

Masterthesis

Morphological classification of bacteria colonies using machine learning techniques

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Abstract

The *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain SBW25 is a crucial model organism at the Max-Planck Institute for microbial population biology, evolutionary genetics, and plant-microbe interaction studies. By utilizing fluorescence and phase contrast microscopy, researchers can determine specific phenotypic and morphological traits impacted by genetic changes, external selection pressures, environmental factors, and competition. Over time, this research has produced a significant and constantly developing set of microscopic images. Sadly, the examination of these images frequently requires diligent attention and demands extensive manual labour. To tackle this inflating data promptly, automated workflows are essential, most notably for activities such as gauging and tracing cell numbers, shapes, and dimensions.

The aim of this master thesis project is to devise an image segmentation workflow employing deep artificial neural networks to scrutinise the colonies of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* SBW25. The workflow consists of two primary stages: segmentation, which involves the generation of masks around the colonies, and classification, which aims to differentiate various morphological types. To tackle this challenge, we will utilise cutting-edge segmentation methods to devise a customised workflow fit for this particular issue.

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1 Motivation

In recent years, biology has experienced an unparalleled surge in the magnitude and intricacy of data produced by various sources [1]. This influx of data, commonly known as "big data," has led to a paradigmatic shift in scientific inquiry across various disciplines. It poses significant challenges and offers remarkable opportunities for enhancing our knowledge of biological systems, with the potential to make groundbreaking discoveries in areas such as disease research, drug development, and environmental studies.

The increasing efficiency of data generation within shorter timeframes presents numerous challenges that necessitate the application of information technology methods. These challenges span the complete data lifecycle, from acquisition and storage to distribution and analysis, and are not limited to specific types of data. In the field of microbiology, extensive image databases are now available to researchers, offering detailed insights into the morphology, spatial distribution, and temporal behaviors of bacterial colonies. This wealth of data holds immense potential, but sophisticated computational techniques are required to unlock its value, especially in the areas of image segmentation and classification.

Traditional methods of biological image analysis frequently require manual intervention from researchers. This necessitates time-consuming and laborious tasks, such as image data annotation, segmentation, and classification. However, the rapid expansion in the size and complexity of biological image datasets has rendered manual analysis impractical and, at times, insurmountable. Efficiently extracting meaningful information from these datasets is vital for the advancement of biological knowledge. This is a significant bottleneck for researchers to overcome.

Deep Learning (DL), a subdivision of artificial intelligence, is an efficient and innovative technique that can automate and enhance numerous aspects of biological image analysis [2]. DL algorithms, notably Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)s, are advanced in feature extraction and pattern recognition, which makes them ideally suited for analysing complex and heterogeneous biological images [3]. By utilizing deep learning techniques, researchers can greatly improve the efficiency and accuracy of analyzing images, ultimately leading to a deeper comprehension of biological phenomena and enabling the discovery of new knowledge.

The Department of Microbial Population Biology (MPB) at the Max-Planck-Institute (MPI) for Evolutionary Biology in Plön conducts extensive research on the model organism, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain SBW25 [4]. This bacterium thrives in soil and water ecosystems and has aroused significant interest due to its potential for enhancing the growth of host plants, particularly in agricultural settings [5]. A substantial area of research strives to characterise SBW25 colonies based on their morphological features, thus demanding accurate classification and segmentation of colonies in microscopy images.

The vast amount of data created by scientists in Molecular and Cellular Biology (MCB) makes it unfeasible to manually analyse all images collected. But it should be highlighted that although this challenge exists, manual analysis remains a widespread practice today. To combat this challenge, automated workflows are not only beneficial but crucial. Artificial intelligence, particularly Deep Learning, has demonstrated superior efficiency and lower error rates compared to manual workflows in performing segmentation and classification tasks [2].

While several research groups have developed tools for DL tasks in recent years and made them publicly available, these tools often cater to specific tasks or organisms and may not

align precisely with the unique demands of particular research problems. Consequently, creating a workflow typically necessitates the development of a new tool or the adaptation of an existing one.

In light of these considerations, this study embarks on the development of a customized workflow for the segmentation and classification of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* SBW25 colonies. This workflow, spanning data preparation, segmentation, and classification steps, seeks to harness the power of Deep Learning to provide researchers at the MPB with a workflow for their image analysis requirements. The ultimate objective is to expedite research, enhance data-driven decision-making, and unlock novel insights into the behavior and characteristics of SBW25 colonies.

This thesis is organized as follows: The first section delves into the theoretical underpinnings of classification in Chapter 2, followed by an exploration of image segmentation in Chapter 3, and an examination of Deep Learning in Chapter 4. Image segmentation constitutes a crucial process in computer vision, implicating the division of an image into distinct, significant regions or objects. The research examines diverse segmentation approaches, such as region-based, boundary-based, and machine learning techniques.

Deep Learning (DL), a subfield of machine learning, has been revered for its significant impact on image processing, due to the introduction of neural networks. This section will discuss the fundamental concepts of DL, including Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)s, transformer networks and vision transformers, all of which play a crucial role in automating image analysis tasks and improving accuracy and efficiency. This section provides a strong basis in image segmentation and Deep Learning, delivering relevant background information on subsequent practical work.

The following section examines and discusses commonly used segmentation libraries in chapter 6, assessing their effectiveness within the workflow and contribution to the overall process.

This is followed by a detailed explanation of the classification process in chapter 7.

Chapter 8 of this thesis provides a thorough account of the segmentation and classification workflow, connecting the theoretical concepts previously discussed to practical application. It starts by outlining the essential requirements for developing this workflow.

The thesis's final section in chapter 9 provides a summary of the vital findings and insights obtained during the research. The work's practical applications are then discussed, highlighting its potential benefit in various real-world settings. The conclusion draws upon this information to offer suggestions for future improvements and expansions. Recommendations are put forth to explore innovative segmentation techniques, ameliorate model performance, and expand the capabilities of the workflow.

2 Classification

Classification is a fundamental task in machine learning and pattern recognition. It involves the process of categorizing input data into predefined classes or categories based on their inherent characteristics. The Classification process consists of the following steps: It begins with collecting and curating a dataset containing labeled samples, where each example is associated with a class label. The data is first pre-processed to ensure its quality, consistency and relevance. This involves normalization, removal of outliers and possible augmentation. Following data collection and pre-processing, feature extraction and selection are carried out in non-deep learning settings. It is possible that raw data may not be directly usable for classification in some cases.

An extraction of meaningful Features is performed on the data to transform it into a suitable representation. Feature selection techniques may also be applied to retain only the most informative attributes, reducing the dimensionality and improving efficiency. The classification of new data requires the training of a suitable classification model. As a result, the next step involves training a classifier. Various machine learning algorithms can be used for this purpose, which will be introduced later. Analyzing the quality of a model requires an evaluation phase. The trained model's performance is assessed using evaluation metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix on a separate, unseen validation dataset. After creating a suitable model, it can be deployed to classify new, unseen data in real-world scenarios.

2.1 Popular Classification Algorithms

Several popular classification algorithms have been widely used in machine learning and data science for various applications. These algorithms are capable of classifying segmented bacteria colonies based on their characteristics. In the following some of the most well-known and commonly used classification algorithms get introduced.

2.1.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is a statistical method used for binary classification tasks, where the goal is to predict whether an instance belongs to one of two classes [6].

Logistic Regression is commonly used in fields such as medical research, finance, and social sciences to predict binary outcomes. Example applications include deciding whether a customer will churn or not, whether an email is spam or not, etc. While Logistic Regression is primarily used for binary classification, it can be extended to handle multiclass problems. One common approach is the "One-vs-Rest" (OvR) or "One-vs-All" approach, where a separate binary logistic regression model is trained for each class, treating it as the positive class and the rest as the negative class. The class with the highest predicted probability is then assigned as the final classification. In machine learning, it is a fundamental building block and the basis for more complex classification algorithms.

Logistic Regression, although widely applicable, has its limitations. It assumes that the relationship between the features and the log odds of the outcome is linear. If the relationship is highly non-linear, other machine learning models like decision trees or neural networks might perform better. Additionally, Logistic Regression is not well-suited for problems with imbalanced datasets where one class significantly outnumbers the other [6].

2.1.2 Support Vector Machines

A **Support Vector Machine (SVM)** is a powerful and versatile classification algorithms widely used in machine learning and pattern recognition. It can be used for binary and multi-class classification tasks. Given a set of labeled data points, SVM aims to find a hyperplane that maximizes the margin between classes [7]. The margin is defined as the perpendicular distance between the hyperplane and the closest data points from both classes. This algorithm solves a quadratic optimization problem to find the hyperplane that maximizes the margin while ensuring that the data points are correctly classified. SVMs work well in high-dimensional spaces, which makes them suitable for tasks with a large number of features [8]. Furthermore, it focus on the support vectors, which are the closest points to the decision boundary. Outliers that are far from the decision boundary have less impact. SVMs are capable of handling non-linear relationships in data by applying transformations of the feature space.

A potential limitation of SVMs is their reliance on hyperparameter selection, including the choice of kernel function, regularization parameter, and margin. These hyperparameters have the potential to impact the performance and generalizability of the SVM model, necessitating thorough tuning and validation. Additionally, SVMs may be computationally demanding, particularly for extensive datasets with numerous characteristics and categories. Furthermore, Support Vector Machines (SVMs) may not perform optimally in the presence of noisy or imbalanced data, wherein the classes are not well-separated or have different proportions [9].

2.1.3 Decision Trees

Decision Trees are a supervised learning algorithm primarily used for classification, but can also be employed for regression. They operate by recursively dividing the data into subsets based on input feature values. At each stage, a feature is chosen to partition the data into classes or to predict the target variable with the minimum error. The process persists until reaching a stopping criterion, which produces a tree-shaped form where every terminal node represents a class label or predicted value. A chief benefit of decision trees is their simplicity and user-friendliness, offering vivid visualisations and comprehension of feature significance and decision-making procedures. Nevertheless, they are prone to overfitting, particularly in complex datasets [10].

2.1.4 Random Forest

The **Random Forest** algorithm is an ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to improve the accuracy of classification and regression tasks, and to mitigate the risk of overfitting [11]. The individual decision trees are trained using random subsets of the data and features, forming a “forest” of trees. The final prediction is obtained by aggregating the predictions of the individual trees, either through a majority vote for classification tasks or averaging for regression tasks. Random Forests are known for their robustness, their ability to handle noisy data effectively, and their reduced susceptibility to overfitting compared to single decision trees.

Decision trees can be as effective as deep neural networks (DNNs) for certain tasks and should be seen as a viable alternative option. Nevertheless, one significant disadvantage of using decision trees is the ‘Black Box’ nature, whereby the method they employ to arrive

at decisions is difficult to trace and analyse [12]. This creates a challenge in comprehending why a particular choice was made, particularly in complex, extensively branching trees.

2.1.5 Gradient Boosting

Gradient Boosting is a potent machine learning technique that serves both classification and regression tasks [13]. It is a member of the ensemble learning algorithm family, employing multiple weak learners to form a robust predictive model.

The primary concept of gradient boosting is to generate a sequence of weak models progressively and correct any mistakes made in the previous ones. This is accomplished by training each new model to predict the residuals (i.e. the differences between the actual values and the predictions of the ensemble so far) of the previous models [13]. The term "gradient" refers to the fact that it optimizes the loss function's gradient with respect to the predictions of the ensemble.

This approach can also be extended to the decision tree. In the context of gradient boosted decision trees, a succession of decision trees are added to the ensemble one after the other [14]. The initial tree is frequently a shallow instance or a fundamental constant forecast. Successive trees are educated to forecast the residuals that have been left by the preceding trees. The concluding forecast is produced by amalgamating the predictions of every single tree within the collection [14].

2.1.6 Neural Networks

Because of their ability to automatically learn complex relationships and patterns within data, Neural Networks are highly effective for a wide range of classification tasks. Neural networks require substantial amounts of labeled data for training, and their complexity demands significant computational resources. Overfitting can occur if the model is too large or the training dataset is small. Mitigating these challenges requires a proper architecture design, regularization techniques, and careful tuning.

A range of neural network architectures has been created to tackle classification tasks, taking into account particular challenges and data types, which provides successful solutions to various classification problems.

Dense Neural Networks (DNNs) were introduced at the beginning of artificial neural networks and have been found to be adaptable and particularly effective with structured data. Their documented ability to uncover intricate patterns is noteworthy.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) specialize in sequential data and manage temporal dependencies. They have practical use in tasks where sequencing data is crucial, like natural language processing and speech recognition.

Conversely, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are precisely engineered for activities related to images. They are intended for image categorisation, relying on convolutional layers to independently draw hierarchical features from pictures. They are skilled at capturing spatial patterns by applying filters and reducing spatial dimensions through pooling layers. This design makes them especially proficient in detecting objects within images, particularly in scenarios where translation invariance is vital.

Each architecture has its own distinct strengths and purposes, which contribute to the broad spectrum of classification solutions in the neural network field.

Another significant advancement in the field of neural networks is called Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). GANs comprise two primary components: a generator and a discriminator, which undergo simultaneous training through a competitive process. The generator creates counterfeit data samples, and the discriminator evaluates these samples, delivering feedback on their credibility. The generator utilises this feedback to enhance its output, thereby making the generated data more authentic. The discriminator adjusts to distinguish between real and generated data. This process continues until the generator produces data that is almost indistinguishable from real data and the discriminator cannot differentiate between them.

The recent development of language model-based chatbots like ChatGPT [15] showed the power of **Transformer Networks** [16] to the public. Transformers have gained popularity in natural language processing tasks due to their exceptional performance in capturing contextual relationships in text. They use self-attention mechanisms to process input data in parallel, enabling the model to focus on relevant parts of the input sequence. Using Vision Transformer [17], this architecture can also be used for classification.

2.2 Classification Metrics

Various metrics measure the performance of a classification algorithm, as explained below. In the context of classification tasks, several key terms are used to compare the predicted labels generated by a classification algorithm with the actual or "ground truth" labels. These terms form the basis for various metrics that assess the classification algorithm's performance. The key terms can be described as [18]:

- **TP (True Positive):** Objects that were correctly predicted as belonging to the class.
- **TN (True Negative):** Objects that were correctly classified as not belonging to the class.
- **FP (False Positive):** Objects that were falsely predicted as belonging to the class.
- **FN (False Negative):** Objects that were falsely predicted as not belonging to the class.

These terms are used in various performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, the F1 score, and others. Each of these metrics offers a different perspective on the classification algorithm's performance, and they are often used together to gain a comprehensive understanding of its performance.

2.2.1 Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix is a fundamental tool in machine learning and statistics for evaluating the performance of classification models. It compares the actual and predicted labels of a dataset and summarizes the results in a two-dimensional matrix:

$$\text{Confusion Matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{TP} & \text{FN} \\ \text{FP} & \text{TN} \end{bmatrix}$$

A confusion matrix can be used to calculate various metrics for a classification model, including accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1 score [18]. Confusion matrices help understand the strengths and weaknesses of a classification model, showing where the model makes errors, whether it is more prone to false positives or false negatives, and how well it performs overall.

2.2.2 Accuracy

Accuracy is a common metric for classification tasks, measuring the percentage of correctly classified instances among all instances in the dataset [18]. It can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

While accuracy is a valuable metric, it can be deceptive when dealing with imbalanced datasets. In such instances, accuracy may not present an accurate depiction of a model's true performance since it tends to favour the majority class. As a result, even if a model excels at identifying the majority class but performs poorly on the minority class, it may still achieve a high accuracy [19].

2.2.3 Precision, Recall, and F1 Score

Precision

Also known as Positive Predictive Value (PPV), precision is the probability that when an object is predicted to belong to a class, it will actually belong to that class [18]. It can be described as:

$$\text{PPV} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

High precision implies that the model rarely misidentifies a negative sample as positive. Essentially, it measures the model's capability to label an instance as positive only with a high degree of confidence. This reduces the likelihood of false positives, which in turn mitigates the possibility of erroneously classifying a negative sample as positive [18].

Recall

Also known as Sensitivity or True Positive Rate, recall measures the ability of a model to identify all relevant positive instances in the dataset [19]. It can be described as:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

A high recall indicates that the model is proficient in precisely capturing and identifying positive instances. This suggests that the model has a remarkable aptitude to detect and incorporate as many actual positive cases as conceivable in its anticipations [18]. In essence, a high-recall model lessens the probability of overlooking meaningful positive instances, ensuring that only a minimal number of genuine positives are overlooked.

F1 Score

The F1 score is a balance between precision and recall, particularly useful when balancing false positives and false negatives is desired [19]. It is the harmonic mean of precision and recall and can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{F1 Score} = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (4)$$

The F1 Score is a robust metric for situations where precision or recall is particularly low, as the harmonic mean places more weight on lower values. This makes it ideal for situations with different costs for false positives and false negatives, or when balanced performance is required [19].

2.2.4 Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve and Area Under the Curve

Another popular metrics for classification are the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve and Area Under the Curve (AUC). Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve plots the true positive rate against the false positive rate at various classification thresholds [20]. A steeper ROC curve indicates that the model has a higher discriminative power, meaning it can better distinguish between positive and negative cases. Additionally, a ROC curve that is closer to the top-left corner represents a superior model in terms of classification performance. A diagonal line from the bottom-left to the top-right represents a random guessing classifier [21]. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) represents the area under the ROC curve, providing a single scalar value to assess the classifier's performance across different thresholds [20]. The formula for AUC is as follows:

$$\text{AUC} = \int \text{ROC curve } dx$$

In conclusion, Precision, Recall, and the F1 Score are crucial for evaluating the performance of classification models. The information provided offers valuable insights into the model's effectiveness at distinguishing between positive and negative instances. It aids in the informed decision-making regarding model selection and parameter tuning.

3 Image Segmentation

Image segmentation is a fundamental task in computer vision and image processing that aims to divide an image into meaningful and semantically coherent regions. The goal is to separate different regions or objects of an image of interest from the background or from each other. Image segmentation is essential in various applications, including object recognition, medical imaging, autonomous vehicles, and more. In this chapter, we introduce the different types of image segmentation and the most common segmentation techniques.

3.1 Semantic and instance segmentation

Semantic and instance segmentation are two distinct types of image segmentation. Semantic segmentation is a pixel-level classification task that assigns a label to each pixel in an image.

Figure 1: Comparison of binary image (left), instance segmentation (middle), and semantic segmentation (right) [22].

It aims to divide an image into regions of interest based on their category or class. Each pixel in a segmented region is assigned the same label representing the object to which it belongs. This technique does not provide identification of individual instances. To identify individual objects, instance segmentation can be used. It goes beyond semantic segmentation by not only classifying pixels into object categories, but also distinguishing individual instances of objects. Each instance is assigned a unique label, allowing the system to identify and distinguish between separate occurrences of the same class.

3.2 Image Segmentation Techniques

There are a variety of algorithms for segmenting images. By using this algorithm, the amount of manual effort can be reduced. Therefore, we are introducing common image segmentation techniques.

3.2.1 Threshold-based Segmentation

Segmentation with the help of thresholds is a simple and widely used technique in image processing and computer vision for separating objects or regions of interest from the background. The method operates on grayscale images, where pixels with intensity values above

or below a specified threshold are classified as foreground or background, respectively. By adjusting the threshold value, the segmentation sensitivity can be controlled, so that objects of interest can be extracted based on their pixel intensity characteristics [23]. Despite threshold-based segmentation's simplicity and computation efficiency, it can be limited in cases of complex lighting conditions, variations in intensity, or overlapping objects. For many applications, threshold-based segmentation remains an attractive and useful approach, such as basic object extraction and preliminary image preprocessing.

3.2.2 Edge-based Segmentation

Edge-based segmentation focuses on detecting and highlighting abrupt changes in pixel intensities, known as edges, to delineate object boundaries. This technique is particularly useful when objects in the image have distinct boundaries or when the goal is to identify details and shapes [23]. Edge detection algorithms such as Canny, Sobek, and Prewitt, analyze pixel intensity gradients to identify regions of rapid changes, indicating potential object edges. The contours of an object can be created by connecting these edges. Edge-based segmentation is computationally efficient and can provide valuable information about object boundaries, making it suitable for applications like object recognition, shape analysis, and image preprocessing. This technique can be limited, in cases where objects have fuzzy or poorly defined boundaries. Therefore, edge-based segmentation is often used in combination with other segmentation methods to achieve more robust results in various image analysis tasks.

3.2.3 Region-based Segmentation

Segmentation algorithms that are region-based, group pixels with similar attributes, such as color, texture, or intensity, into coherent regions or segments. Unlike edge-based segmentation which focuses on detecting abrupt changes in pixel intensities, region-based methods aim to find areas with homogeneous properties within the image [23]. By applying clustering algorithms, the image gets partitioned into regions based on pixel similarity. These regions represent distinct objects or regions of interest within the image. This segmentation approach is particularly effective in handling images with varying lighting conditions, noise, and overlapping objects. It can also be used to segment textured or patterned regions effectively. However, it is difficult to determine the optimal number of regions or the appropriate Features for clustering. This technique can be limited, in cases with irregular or complex shapes. In this case, a combination of edge-based and region-based techniques might be more suitable. A typical region-based algorithm is called Watershed [24], which is inspired by the concept of watersheds in hydrology.

3.2.4 Neural Networks for Segmentation

Segmentation with Neural Network, specifically Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)s, has revolutionized the field of image segmentation. Since the segmentation problem can be seen as classification into classes, the algorithms introduced in chapter 2 can also be applied to this task. In addition, special techniques have been developed for this task, which are presented in the following.

Unlike traditional segmentation techniques that rely on handcrafted features, neural networks can automatically learn hierarchical representations from raw data, making them

highly effective for complex image analysis tasks. CNNs are widely used for semantic and instance segmentation. For semantic segmentation, Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs) [25] and U-Net [26] architectures are popular choices. For instance segmentation, Mask R-CNN [27] is a dominant architecture. It extends the Faster R-CNN [28] object detection framework with an additional mask prediction branch, enabling pixel-wise segmentation masks for each detected object instance.

Before segmentation, all of these segmentation CNNs must be trained. Training segmentation neural networks require large annotated datasets. To address data scarcity, data augmentation techniques such as flipping, rotating, scaling, and introducing geometric deformations are commonly applied to generate additional training samples. This improves the generalization and robustness of the model, but remains subprime compared to a larger dataset in the first place.

To train segmentation networks effectively, specialized loss functions are used, which will be introduced in the metrics chapter. Pretrained CNN models can be used as a starting point to reduce the effort involved in producing data for training. With the help of transfer learning, this model can be fine-tuned by training its own data for better segmentation results.

Despite the significant advancements in image segmentation brought about by neural networks, there are still challenges to overcome. These include dealing with class imbalance, accurately segmenting objects with unclear boundaries, and preventing overfitting. Researchers and practitioners are continuously working on these issues to further improve the performance of neural networks in image segmentation tasks.

They offer highly precise and adaptable solutions for both semantic and instance segmentation tasks, thereby significantly enhancing our ability to understand and interpret images. In contrast to traditional segmentation techniques and to other ML techniques, neural networks can learn complex and non-linear patterns from data, making them suitable for various segmentation challenges.

3.3 Segmentation Metrics

Metrics play a crucial role in evaluating the performance of segmentation tasks, providing quantitative measures of how well the algorithms perform on specific datasets. Therefore a test dataset must be collected, containing a ground truth, which can be compared with the predicted segmentation created by the algorithm. In this chapter, we want to introduce the most important metrics. For different calculations, important terms for comparison of ground truth and predictions in terms of segmentation tasks are [18]:

- TP: True Positive, the pixels were correctly predicted belonging to the class.
- TN: True negative, the pixels were correctly classified as not belonging to the class.
- FP: False positive, the pixels were falsely predicted as belonging to the class.
- FN: False Negative: The pixels were falsely predicted as not belonging to the class.

3.3.1 Pixel accuracy

Pixel Accuracy (PA) measures the percentage of correctly classified pixels in the segmentation mask. It can be calculated for each class separately and can be described as:

$$PA = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K p_{ii}}{\sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}} \quad (5)$$

Where K is the number of classes, i.e. in our binary segmentation, where the pixel either belongs to a cell or it is not belonging to the cell. p_{ii} is the number of correctly classified pixels, i.e. belonging to class i and predicted to belong to class i , in our binary segmentation this equals $TP + TN$. p_{ij} is the number of pixel belonging to class i , but being predicted as belonging to class j , in our binary classification this equals $FP + FN$.

The pixel accuracy averaged over all classes is known as **Mean Pixel Accuracy** and can be described as follows:

$$MPA = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{p_{ii}}{\sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}} \quad (6)$$

The results of pixel accuracy can be misleading for imbalanced datasets where one class dominates, i.e. a high pixel accuracy score without actually giving insight if the class is predicted correctly [29].

3.3.2 Intersection over Union / Jaccard Index

Intersection over Union / Jaccard Index measures the overlap between predicted segmentation and the ground truth masks [30].

$$IoU = J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN + FP} \quad (7)$$

Where A is the ground truth segmentation and B is the predicted segmentation. The IoU is calculated per class, and the average of the IoUs of all classes is known as the `textbfMean IoU`.

3.3.3 Dice Coefficient

Similar to IoU, the **Dice Coefficient (DC)** measures the similarity between the predicted and ground truth segmentation masks and is defined as twice the size of the intersection divided by the sum of the sizes of the two masks [29]. Formally it can be described as follows:

$$DC = \frac{2 |A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|} \quad (8)$$

3.3.4 Precision/Recall/F1 score

These metrics are very versatile and are computable for segmentation and classification tasks. The definition of these metrics can be found in chapter 2.2.3.

4 Deep Learning

Deep Learning (DL), a part of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is among the most exciting and rapidly evolving fields in computer science today. These technologies are changing the way we live, work, and communicate with each other. Artificial Intelligence is an area of computer science that focuses on creating machines that can think and learn like humans. Neural Networks are the foundation of Deep Learning. They are inspired by the structure and function of the human brain and are therefore called artificial neural networks [31].

Early research in Neural Networks was focused on developing simple models of artificial neurons and studying their computational properties. In the 1950s and 60s, researchers such as Frank Rosenblatt and Marvin Minsky developed the first artificial neural networks based on the perceptron model. In the 1980s, Neural Networks research gained renewed interest with the development of the backpropagation algorithm, which allowed for more complex neural network architectures to be trained on large datasets [31]. These achievements led to the development of the multi-layer perceptron and the resurgence of Neural Networks research.

Since then, research in Neural Networks has focused on developing more complex and efficient architectures, improving training algorithms, and applying Neural Networks to a wide range of applications. One of the most significant developments in Neural Networks research has been the development of Deep Learning, which led to breakthroughs in computer vision, natural language processing, and other areas.

NNs are made up of layers of interconnected nodes or artificial neurons. Each neuron receives input from the neurons in the previous layer, processes the information, and sends its output to the neurons in the next layer. The output of the last layer of neurons is the network's final output.

Figure 2: Biological neuron (left) and artificial neuron (right). Adapted from Ref. [32].

A single neuron receives information in the form of electrical signals. These received signals are added, compared to a threshold and if the sum exceeds the threshold, the neuron sends a new signal. Figure 2 shows how inputs from x_0 to x_n gets multiplied by corresponding weights w_i leads to an output y . The input $x_0 = 1$ contains a special bias b , which is a

number belonging to the specific neuron. This bias affects the function of several neurons in a neural network.

NNs can also be called artificial neural networks built from artificial neurons, called perceptrons. The structure of a NN can be seen in Figure 3. NNs consists of three layers: the input layer, the hidden layer, and the output layer. The input layer is the first layer of the neural network and is responsible for receiving the input data. Each perceptron in the input layer represents a feature of the input data, such as the color, shape, or size of an image [31].

The hidden layer is located between the input and output layers and is responsible for processing the input data. It consists of multiple perceptrons, each of which receives input from the previous layer and performs a mathematical operation on the data before passing it on to the next layer [31].

The output layer is the final layer of the Neural Network and is responsible for producing the output based on the input data. Each perceptron in the output layer represents a possible output, such as a classification or a regression value. The connections between the perceptrons in the different layers are represented by weights, which are adjusted during the training process to optimize the network's performance.

The output signal of a perceptron is determined by its activation function, which takes into account the input signal and weights. Thus, it is necessary to have the output of a single perceptron, which can be described as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i w_i + b_i \quad (9)$$

The Sum from Equation 9 gets passed to an activation function, which determines the further passing on of the signal. The weights and biases are the only changeable part of the NN that can be adjusted to get the desired output. This mechanism enables the model to capture complex relationships and dependencies within the input sequences, regardless of their distances.

Figure 3: Artificial neural network [33].

The architecture of artificial neural network is shown in Figure 3. A neural network consists of an Input layer, a number of Hidden layers, and an Output layer. The input layer is the first layer of the neural network and is responsible for receiving external data and passing it on to subsequent layers [31]. Each neuron in the input layer represents a feature or attribute of the input data. For instance, in an image classification task, each neuron could correspond to the intensity value of a pixel. The input layer's neuron count is contingent upon the dimensionality of the input data. For example, if you are handling 100x100 pixel images, the input layer's neuron count would typically be 10,000.

Hidden layers are the intermediary layers situated between the input and output layers. They are referred to as "hidden" because their activation and operations are not readily visible from outside the network [31]. Their task is to carry out intricate transformations on the input data in order to extract significant characteristics and representation. The number of hidden layers and neurons in each layer is a crucial architectural choice and depends on the complexity of the problem.

The final layer of the neural network is commonly referred to as the output layer. Its primary function is to generate predictions or results from the network's inputs [31]. The number of neurons in the output layer relies on the type of problem at hand. For tasks involving binary classification, there may be a solitary neuron that represents the probability of membership to one class. In case of multi-class classification, one neuron is allocated for each respective class.

There are multiple architectures available for DL, but the CNN architecture has garnered significant attention due to its effectiveness in image processing. There are various other architectures built for image analysis and image segmentation, such as recurrent networks or visual attention models. In the forthcoming text, we will elucidate convolutional neural networks, as this is one of the most prominent structures in image processing.

4.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), also known as ConvNets, are a class of Deep Learning models specifically designed for processing and analyzing visual data, such as images and videos [31]. They have revolutionized the field of computer vision and have found applications in various domains, from image classification and object detection to medical image analysis and autonomous driving.

Figure 4: CNN architecture [34].

The CNN architecture comprises a feature learning section and a classification section.

4.1.1 Feature learning section

In the feature learning section of a CNN, the network identifies and extracts important features from the input data [31]. This is accomplished through employing convolutional layers that utilize a series of filters to detect particular patterns in the data. During training, the filters are fine-tuned to pinpoint the most vital attributes for the given task. In addition to the convolutional layer, the feature learning part consists of an activation layer and pooling, which are described below.

The **convolutional layer** employs a filter to extract characteristics such as lines, points, edges, and so forth, from an image. The filter is performed by sliding the filter over the input data and computing the dot product between the filter and the portion of the input data it is currently overlapping [31]. This process is repeated for each location in the input data, producing an activation or feature map that represents the strength and location of the detected feature in the input [35].

One of the key advantages of convolutional layers is their ability to automatically learn filters that are optimized for the specific task at hand. During training, the network learns to adjust the values of the filters to detect features that are important for making accurate predictions [35]. In figure 5 the principle of convolution is visualized.

Figure 5: Principle of convolution [36].

A convolution layer comprises distinct filters that operate autonomously on the input tensor. Their produced outputs are merged to generate a fresh output tensor. Tensors can be represented as multidimensional arrays, with the number of dimensions corresponding to the order of the tensor. For instance, a scalar constitutes a tensor of rank 0, a vector constitutes a tensor of rank 1, and a matrix constitutes a tensor of rank 2. Tensors of higher order can be presented as arrays with over two dimensions. The number of channels within the input tensor can be augmented or diminished by utilizing filters.

In a convolutional layer, the filters should be ordered hierarchically, and each layer utilizes the output of the prior layer. CNNs connect layers locally. This local connectivity allows the network to take advantage of the spatial structure of the input data, such as images, where nearby pixels are often highly correlated. By detecting local patterns, the network can learn to identify important features in the data, such as edges, corners, and textures [37]. Applying typical filters for vertical and horizontal edge detection is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Example: Horizontal and vertical edge detection [38].

This means that in a convolutional neural network, the initial layers capture specific features such as contours, resulting later layers capturing more global features and are less sharp compared to earlier layers.

Activation layers are usually applied to the activation map following a convolutional layer. They introduce non-linearity into the network by transforming the output of the preceding layer. This enables the network to learn complex functions. An activation function takes

a floating-point value as input and produces a new floating-point value as output, which affects the network’s learning process [39]. For image processing, the rectified linear unit (ReLU) is the most frequently utilized activation function in CNNs, which can be computed using c as the sum of the weighted inputs as follows:

$$\text{fact}(c) = f\text{ReLU}(c) = \max(0, c) \quad (10)$$

A rectified linear unit (ReLU) can be presented as a graph, as shown in Figure 7, where negative inputs result in an output of 0.

Figure 7: Example: ReLU with no negative outputs [40].

The ReLU activation function is a rapid and straightforward way to introduce non-linearity. There are several other activation functions used in DL, with sigmoid and tanh being among the most popular. No definitive theory exists for determining the most suitable activation function for a specific layer of a given network in a particular scenario. It is recommended to start with an activation function that has produced satisfactory results in comparable setups and to test alternative options to evaluate their impact on performance [39].

The **pooling layer** is an operation that performs downsampling on the input data. The aim of this process is to decrease the spatial dimensions of the data whilst retaining significant features and connections. Pooling layers work by separating the input data into non-overlapping areas, referred to as pooling regions, and condensing the values within each region via a designated process.

Average pooling and max pooling are the two typical processes used in pooling layers. Average pooling calculates the average value of the input values within each pooling region, while max pooling selects the maximum value.

Figure 8: Example: 2x2 max pooling [41].

Figure 8 illustrates an example of 2x2 maximum pooling. In each colored region, the highest value is calculated. In summary, pooling layers are an important component of CNNs that help to reduce the complexity of the model while preserving important features in the input data.

4.1.2 Classification section

The output layer, also referred to as the final layer, is responsible for producing the eventual output classifications of a neural network. Before reaching the output layer, the data undergoes a flattening process that converts multidimensional data into a one-dimensional vector [31]. This vector is then fed into the fully connected output layer that utilizes a softmax activation function to generate probabilities for every class. The softmax function accepts a vector of real numbers and normalizes it to create a probability distribution consisting of probabilities proportional to the exponential of the input values. The output layer is completely connected, signifying that each neuron in this layer is linked to all the neurons in the preceding layer.

4.2 U-Net

The U-Net architecture is a convolutional neural network specifically created for biologic image segmentation. In 2015, it emerged as the winner of the ISBI cell tracking challenge, and it continues to exhibit impressive performance across diverse biological segmentation tasks, all while maintaining a reasonable training time via GPU utilization.

U-Net is widely regarded as a pioneering technology for the segmentation of cells and may be viewed as a benchmark for image analysis endeavours [42]. One of the primary challenges in utilising DL for biological image analysis centres around the inadequacy of substantial datasets to train networks, impeding the overall effectiveness. To address this constraint, U-Net adopts a strategy of extensive data augmentation by applying elastic deformations to the present training data, thereby enhancing the size of the dataset.

Additionally, this strategy enhances the existing dataset by increasing its diversity. The amount of training data is enhanced through data augmentation in DL, as it enables the network to acquire knowledge on the invariances that are typically found in biological images.

Another difficulty in cell segmentation involves the division of adjacent objects of the same category. To tackle this issue, U-Net incorporates weight maps for each ground truth segmentation, accounting for the differing frequency of pixels across various classes within an image; this ultimately helps to reduce loss during training [26].

The U-Net architecture comprises an encoder-decoder network with a contracting path and an almost symmetric expansive path, creating a U-shaped structure. It utilizes a modified and extended fully convolutional network architecture supplemented with successive layers for upsampling in order to enhance output resolution. U-Net utilizes a modified and extended fully convolutional network architecture supplemented with successive layers for upsampling in order to enhance output resolution.

One essential modification involves a significant number of feature channels in the upsampling section to disseminate contextual information. to higher resolution layers.

The contracting pathway adheres to the typical convolutional network architecture, with the repetition of two 3x3 convolutions, each subsequently accompanied by a ReLU activation function and a 2x2 max pooling layer for downsampling. With each step of downsampling, the feature channel count is doubled. In the upsampling pathway, every upsample is pursued by a 2x2 up-convolution. The number of feature channels is reduced by half, followed by the concatenation with the correspondingly cropped feature map from the contracting path and two 3x3 convolutions, each of which is followed by a ReLU. The final layer is a 1x1 convolution that maps each 64-component feature vector to the desired number of classes. U-Net comprises a total of 23 convolutional layers [26]. The ReLU function’s output serves as a skip connection for the related decoder block.

Figure 9: U-Net architecture [26].

The skip connection is a proven technique that efficiently combines varying levels of abstractions from several layers to produce sharper segmentation maps by supplying additional information.

Computation of the weighted U-Net loss is achieved through pixel-wise soft-max over the feature map and cross-entropy loss function. The classification of each pixel is determined following pixel-wise soft-max combined with cross-entropy among the classes. This transformation converts the segmentation problem into a classification problem, wherein each Pixel classification is required, where each pixel must belong to a specific class.

4.3 ResNet

ResNet, short for Residual Network, is a widely used architecture for deep convolutional neural networks. It was introduced by Kaiming He et al. in their 2016 paper "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition" [43]. ResNet is known for its superior ability to perform various computer vision tasks, especially image classification.

ResNet presents the notion of residual blocks as the cornerstone of its effectiveness. Ordinarily, each layer of a neural network endeavours to comprehend the fundamental mapping between input and output. ResNet's innovation is to implement residual blocks which skip one or more layers and allow the network to learn the residual (the difference between input and output) rather than the full mapping. However, when networks become very deep, the issue of vanishing gradients frequently arises, impeding training. This technique considerably streamlines the training of deep networks.

The Key features of the ResNet architecture can be described as follows:

- **Skip Connections:** Residual blocks with skip connections, also known as identity shortcuts, facilitate gradient flow and enable training of very deep networks.
- **Stacking Blocks:** ResNet consists of multiple building blocks with several residual blocks, increasing network depth for capturing complex features.
- **Pre-Activation:** Many ResNet variants use pre-activation, applying batch normalization and ReLU activation before convolutional layers to address gradient degradation.
- **Bottleneck Architecture:** Deeper ResNets employ a bottleneck architecture with 1x1, 3x3, and 1x1 convolutions to reduce computational complexity while maintaining representational power.
- **Global Average Pooling (GAP):** Instead of fully connected layers, ResNet uses GAP to generate a fixed-sized feature vector from output feature maps, reducing overfitting and adapting to varying input sizes.

ResNets are defined by their depth, represented by the total number of convolutional layers (excluding the initial convolution and final fully connected layers). The widely used ResNet-50 comprises 50 convolutional layers. The network is organized into several building blocks, each including a set of residual blocks. The architecture of ResNet-50 is presented in figure 10.

ResNet 50 has demonstrated exceptional performance for image classification and various other computer vision tasks. It has achieved success in several image recognition competitions, including the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge, and continues to serve as a strong basis for the development of deep neural networks for visual recognition tasks. Its depth and skip connections make it highly effective at capturing intricate image patterns, and it has become a fundamental element of cutting-edge models in the fields of DL and Computer Vision.

Figure 10: The architecture of ResNet-50 [44].

ResNet’s deep architecture enables the capture of intricate and hierarchical features in bacterial colony images. Such colonies could take on a variety of different shapes, sizes and textures, and ResNet’s capacity to learn complex representations renders it suitable for differentiating between bacterial species or colony types.

4.4 Transformer Neural Networks

Transformer neural networks are a revolutionary architectural paradigm in the field of DL, specifically designed to handle sequential and positional data such as language, text, and even images. It was introduced by Vaswani et al. in 2017 [16] and has since become a cornerstone in natural language processing (NLP) and has found applications in various domains.

The key concept of the transformer architecture is the self-attention mechanism, which allows the model to weigh the importance of different parts of the input data when generating output [16]. This mechanism enables the model to capture complex relationships and dependencies within the input sequences, regardless of their distances. The transformer architecture is shown in Figure 11.

Like most neural networks, transformer models are basically large encoder/decoder blocks that process data. At first **Positional Encoders** are used to tag data elements coming into and going out of transformers. Since transformers do not inherently understand the order of the input data, positional encodings are added to the input embeddings to provide information about the positions of words in the sequence [16].

Attention units follow these tags, calculating a kind of algebraic map of how each element relates to the others. Attention queries are typically executed in parallel by calculating a matrix of equations in what’s called multi-headed attention [16]. For each token in the input sequence, three linear transformations are applied independently to create three vectors: Query (Q), Key (K), and Value (V). These transformations allow the model to learn different aspects of the token representations. For each token, the attention scores between the Query (Q) of that token and the Key (K) of all other tokens in the sequence are computed. The

Figure 11: Transformer model architecture [16].

attention scores indicate how much focus should be given to other tokens when processing the current token.

Once the attention scores have been calculated, they are scaled to ensure stable slopes and run through a softmax function to convert them into probability values. This softmax operation causes the scores for each token to sum to 1, effectively creating a weighted distribution over the other tokens in the sequence [16]. This distribution represents the importance or relevance of each token to the current token.

Next, the value (V) vectors are weighted by the attention scores and summed for each token. This weighted sum is what we call the context or attended representation for that token. It encapsulates information from other tokens in the sequence, with the weighting determined by the attention scores.

The final step in the multi-headed attention mechanism is to concatenate the attended representations from all heads and apply another linear transformation to produce the output of the attention layer [45]. This output, often referred to as the context or attended representation, carries information about the relationships and interactions between tokens in the sequence.

These multi-headed attention outputs are then typically passed through feedforward neural networks, which consist of fully connected layers with activation functions such as ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit). These layers allow the model to capture complex and non-linear relationships in the data.

As mentioned above, positional encodings are added to the input embeddings to provide information about the positions of tokens in the sequence. These encodings are typically represented as sine and cosine functions of different frequencies and are added to the input

embeddings element by element [45]. This addition allows the model to distinguish between tokens based on their positions, overcoming the inherent lack of positional information in the original Transformer architecture.

To summarize, the Transformer model utilizes positional encodings to transmit information about token positions. Attention units evaluate the connections between tokens by computing attention scores, which dictate the level of concentration that needs to be applied to other tokens during processing of each token. Those scores are then transformed into weighted distributions over tokens, and the attended representations are produced as weighted sums of token values. Finally, the model processes these attended representations through feedforward networks to capture intricate patterns and correlations present in the data. The incorporation of self-attention and feedforward layers enables Transformers to excel in diverse sequence-to-sequence activities such as natural language processing and computer vision.

4.4.1 Vision Transformer

Vision Transformers (ViTs) [45] represent a groundbreaking development in Computer Vision and Deep Learning, closely related to the Transformer architecture. These models have demonstrated remarkable performance in a variety of computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and most notably, image segmentation. ViTs differ from classical convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in that they don't use convolutional layers. Instead, they transform the input image into a sequence of flattened patches, which are then processed by the Transformer encoder [45]. Each patch is treated as a token, and the self-attention mechanism allows the model to capture global context information efficiently. ViTs have demonstrated competitive performance in comparison to CNNs while being more interpretable and scalable.

Vision Transformers can be used for segmentation tasks effectively in the following ways:

1. **Encoder-Decoder Architectures:** Similar to traditional segmentation models like U-Net [26], you can combine the Vision Transformer's encoder with a decoder network to produce pixel-wise segmentations [45]. The encoder captures contextual information at different scales, while the decoder upsamples and fuses features to generate the final segmentation map.
2. **Patch-wise Segmentation:** Vision Transformers are particularly well-suited for patch-wise segmentation, where each patch in the input image is assigned a class label. This approach benefits from Vision Transformers' ability to handle variable-sized inputs and maintain global context [45]. It is especially useful when fine-grained details are crucial.
3. **Positional Information:** In image segmentation, maintaining accurate positional information is essential. Transformers naturally handle positional encoding, which is crucial for ensuring that the model knows the spatial relationship between different image regions.
4. **Transfer Learning:** Pre-trained Vision Transformers on large datasets, such as ImageNet, can be fine-tuned for segmentation tasks with smaller datasets [45]. This transfer learning strategy leverages the Vision Transformer's ability to extract generic visual features.

5. **Efficient Attention Mechanisms:** To make Vision Transformers computationally efficient for segmentation, you can explore variants with modified attention mechanisms, like sparse attention or convolutional layers in combination with Transformers.

To summarize, Vision Transformers offer a remarkable shift in computer vision, utilising the triumph of Transformers in natural language processing and modifying them to work with grid-like data, such as images. Their self-attention mechanisms, scalability, and capacity to capture the global context make them well-fitted for various computer vision tasks, including image segmentation. They have exhibited promising results and repeatedly remain an area of ongoing research and development.

4.5 Training and Evaluation

Deep Learning (DL) algorithms indeed have the ability to learn to complete tasks autonomously. They do not require manual selection of features or rules for making decisions. Instead, they learn these features by identifying patterns in the input data. The learning process involves adjusting the weights of the connections and the bias of the perceptrons in the network. There are 3 learning strategies which are described below.

4.5.1 Supervised Learning

The most commonly used learning strategy is **supervised learning**, which will be the learning strategy of this work. In supervised learning a special dataset is prepared for the training process. This training dataset provides the input data with corresponding labels [31]. In the case of image segmentation tasks, this dataset consists of a set of images in which for each image a prepared segmentation mask is provided. Data for classification would contain images of single colonies with suitable labels. In the training process, the network adjusts its parameters based on this training dataset. New data can be labeled afterward with these adjusted weights [31].

4.5.2 Unsupervised Learning

Unlike supervised learning, where the model learns to predict a specific target based on labeled examples, **unsupervised learning** aims to find patterns, structures, and relationships within the data without explicit guidance [31]. It is used for clustering or grouping data that is related. This approach can also be used to improve data quality by removing noise or compressing data.

4.5.3 Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement Learning uses a different approach. where the network should learn through trial and error. Afterwards, each result obtained by the network is given a score [31]. The system is basically rewarded for good actions and punished for actions with bad results. When lots of scores are collected, the approach leading to the best results can be selected. New approaches can be tested as patterns change over time, and the one with the best score is kept [31].

4.5.4 Training process

Because most models are trained by supervised learning, we are going to describe the training process for this case. To learn the networks needs a set of training data, which contains input and ground truth, which is a label prepared by manual labor which is seen as the truth. For each example of the training data, the network makes a prediction that is compared to the ground truth. Based on the difference weights are adjusted. The training consists of the following steps:

1. Initialising the values for weights and biases (often randomly).
2. Collect predictions by the network on a set of training data.
3. Calculating the loss by determining the difference between prediction and ground truth.
4. Propagation of the loss back through the network.
5. Update weights and biases using backpropagation information to reduce loss.
6. Repeat steps 2 through 5 iteratively until the model achieves a satisfactory level of performance.

These steps can be divided into 2 phases. The first phase is called **forwardpropagation** and describes when the network makes a prediction for a training sample [31]. The training set is processed by the network, with each neuron in each layer applying its transformation until the final layer generates an output, which is labeled data. In the case of image segmentation, this output is a segmentation mask containing a label for each pixel. The comparison between the prediction and the ground truth is conducted, and a loss function is employed to determine the difference [31].

The loss function that is used depends on the problem. Developing better loss functions for the given scenario is still an active field of research. Typical loss functions that have proven to do well in many networks are **absolute loss**, **mean squared error** and **cross-entropy**. The loss function's result must be nearly zero to suggest an accurate prediction. A zero value would indicate no disparity between the prediction and the ground truth. The network adjusts its weights gradually to achieve a small loss. The next step is known as **backpropagation**, during which the loss is propagated backwards through the network [31]. The term "backpropagation" comes from the backward propagation of the error from the output layer to the input layer, adjusting the weights along the way. This step enables the neural network to learn and improve its performance over successive iterations. In this process, the perceptrons receive only a proportionate share of the total loss, determined by their respective contributions to the output. To modify the weights, an optimizer is utilized. This algorithm adjusts the weights gradually to reduce the loss. Again, various algorithms are frequently employed; some popular examples include gradient descent, stochastic gradient descent, adam - which extends stochastic gradient descent - or adagrad.

An iteration over the whole training dataset is called **Epoch**. The number of samples from the dataset to process before the weights and biases got updated, is called **Batch**. The **Learning rate** is the parameter for the optimizer that determines the scale of weight updates.

While the aim is to minimize the loss, the issue of overfitting is a concern whereby the network learns intricate features of the training set and fails to generalize on new data. A crucial principle for achieving a reliable generalization is to divide the dataset into training

and validation datasets. The training dataset is used to change parameters, while validation data is used to evaluate performance. There are various methods for dividing the dataset, while techniques like early stopping and data augmentation have been effective in preventing overfitting. However, it is recommended to reserve a test set for assessment once the training is complete. To prevent bias, it is crucial that the network has not been exposed to these samples during training.

Another method for avoiding model overfitting is to implement cross-validation. Cross-validation helps mitigate this issue by using the initial training data to generate several mini-train-test splits. These splits are used to tune the model and estimate its performance on unseen data. In conventional k-fold cross-validation, data is divided into k subsets, commonly referred to as folds. The model is trained on k-1 folds and evaluated on the remaining fold. This process is repeated k times, with each fold serving as the test set once. Over the k iterations, the performance of the model is then averaged [46].

4.5.5 Performance Evaluation

To assess the performance of the NN, various quality criteria can be examined. In chapter 3.3 and chapter 2.2, the metrics for segmentation and classification are introduced to evaluate the predictions' quality. To calculate the metrics, the preparation of a test set is required [31]. The validation dataset, which has been utilized to optimize the network parameters, cannot be employed for such purposes due to the leakage of its data to the network, albeit it was not directly used for training. For the evaluation process, metrics are selected based on the task at hand [31]. The calculations of values are presented objectively to describe the network's performance and enable measurement.

In addition to assessing the results produced by a network, it is also possible to evaluate the network itself. This can be done by examining factors such as memory usage, hardware requirements, or the time required to generate predictions. These factors can affect the scalability, efficiency, and usability of the network in practical scenarios. For example, a network that consumes too much memory or takes too long to make predictions may not be suitable for real-time applications or devices with limited resources. Therefore, it is important to consider these factors when designing and selecting a network for a specific task.

5 Data preprocessing

5.1 Data

The provided dataset consists of 92 *jpg* images of 5 different morphological colony types. The images have a resolution of 1280 x 960 pixels. All colony shapes are mutants of the "Wrinkly Spreader" morphotype, which can be caused by various mutations shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Overview: Bacterial Colony Morphology.

The 92 images are distributed among the colony shapes as follows:

- 0085: 3 images
- awsX: 29 images
- mwsR: 19 images
- wspF: 19 images
- wt: 4 images
- mix: 18 images

The mixed images contain various colony shapes. An Example of this mix images is shown in figure 13.

Figure 13: Example: Mix image.

For the Evaluation of segmentation algorithms and the training of special algorithms, a training/ evaluation dataset has to be created. To create a dataset the scientists at the MPI provided images of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* SBW25 colonies.

5.2 Creating Training Data

In Order to evaluate existing segmentation algorithms or train new algorithms a ground truth for each image has to be created. The manual annotation of the images is a time-consuming process and takes from 20 minutes to nearly an hour per image.

The images were annotated using QuPath [47] software. QuPath is an open-source digital pathology software designed for the analysis, visualization, and management of histopathology image data. Figure 14 shows how the UI of QuPath looks like.

Figure 14: Annotation with QuPath.

It is specifically tailored for researchers, pathologists, and scientists working in the field of pathology and image analysis. This software can also be used for annotation purposes. These annotations are valuable for training machine learning algorithms because they can be exported as labels, binary, or instance masks. To maintain organization and facilitate further analysis, it's prudent to create a new QuPath project for the images. It is then possible to import all images into this project. Annotation is an imperative step in image analysis workflows, especially in the sphere of biology, where precise annotations are crucial for assignments such as object detection, segmentation, and classification. The annotation process with QuPath can be divided in the following steps:

1. Creating a Project:

- (a) Launch QuPath and create a new project.
- (b) Define project settings, such as metadata, objectives, and analysis goals.
- (c) Specify the project's storage location on your computer.

2. Loading Images:

- (a) Import digital images into your QuPath project. This can be done through the "File" menu or by dragging and dropping images into QuPath.
- (b) QuPath supports a variety of image formats, including whole-slide images (WSIs).

3. Initial Image Exploration:

- (a) Once the images are loaded, explore them using QuPath's image viewer.
- (b) Use navigation tools to zoom in, pan, and navigate within the images to identify regions of interest (ROIs) for annotation.

4. Creating Annotation Layers:

- (a) Start the annotation process by creating annotation layers. This can be done by selecting "Annotations" in the main menu and choosing "Create new annotation."
- (b) Define the annotation type (e.g., area, point, line, or polygon) based on your annotation needs.

5. Manual Annotation:

- (a) Manually annotate ROIs within the images using the selected annotation tools.
- (b) You can draw, click, or outline areas, add points, or create lines as needed.
- (c) Annotate different structures, such as tissues, cells, or lesions, based on your research or diagnostic objectives.

6. Annotation Attributes:

- (a) Enrich your annotations by adding attributes, labels, descriptions, or classifications.
- (b) These attributes provide context and metadata for the annotated regions.

7. Quality Control:

- (a) Review and validate your annotations for accuracy, completeness, and consistency.
- (b) Make any necessary adjustments or corrections to ensure high-quality annotations.

8. Automation and Batch Annotation:

- (a) Utilize QuPath's automation features, including object detection algorithms, to assist in annotation tasks.
- (b) For large-scale projects, consider batch annotation to automate repetitive tasks across multiple images.

9. Export Annotations with Groovy Scripts:

- (a) QuPath offers extensive scripting capabilities using the Groovy scripting language.
- (b) To export annotations using Groovy scripts, you can follow these steps:
 - i. Write a Groovy script within QuPath's scripting environment.
 - ii. Define the export criteria and format (e.g., CSV, JSON, XML) in your script.
 - iii. Use QuPath's scripting functions to access and export annotation data.
 - iv. Run the script to export annotations according to your specified criteria.

For this described process we provide two Groovy scripts for exporting binary or instance masks. They can be found in the *annotating* folder.

The script for the instance masks is taken from an image annotation tutorial with QuPath which can be found online [48]. Because the export of this masks were needed as binary masks, this script was adapted to the concrete use case. The script offers some user setting for only processing a special channel of interest, using downsampling and image file convention. The annotation are filled with pixel values of 255 (white) on a black background. All exported

images and masks are saved as tiff files with the same name as the input image. The folder directory for the output can be seen in the figure 15 below.

Figure 15: Annotation export structure.

This script generates a “ground_truth” folder in the QuPath project, which houses the annotations. The images and masks are stored in their respective subfolders, “images” and “masks”.

With the usages of different scripts QuPath facilitates the exportation of annotations in various formats, resulting in its broad utility and integration into a machine learning workflow. Nevertheless, this aspect of the workflow demands significant manual effort since the majority of the mask must be drawn by hand. Some annotation tools have been tested, and a few offer automated annotation features with the assistance of pre-trained models. In the future, a newly developed QuPath extension [49] that employs the SegAnything model could drastically expedite this process. Currently, multipurpose segmentation models do not perform as well as necessary on biological images. As time progresses, the use of these models may eventually become standard practice for the annotation process. After importing all images, every image can be processed by using the annotation tools. Once the colonies have been fully segmented, it is possible to process them further.

6 Segmentation Strategies and Performance

One crucial factor in creating a segmentation and classification workflow for bio images is selecting the appropriate segmentation algorithms or libraries. This section will examine alternative options for segmenting colony images to incorporate the technology into the workflow.

6.1 Segment Anything

Segment Anything was recently introduced by the META AI Research Team in April 2023 [50]. It contains the Segment Anything Model (SAM) for promptable segmentation, along with the SA-1B dataset. SAM is designed to perform image segmentation tasks without task-specific training, and it consists of an image encoder, a prompt encoder, and a mask decoder. The corresponding SA-1B dataset contains over 1 billion masks on 11 million images and is diverse and of high quality.

Figure 16: Segment Anything Model (SAM) [50].

The architecture of SAM is shown in figure 16. The image encoder is based on a pretrained Vision Transformer (ViT) [45] that is adapted to process high-resolution inputs. It runs once per image and can be applied before prompting the model. The prompt encoder handles two types of prompts: sparse prompts (points, boxes, text) and dense prompts (masks). Points and boxes are represented using positional encodings, while free-form text is encoded using an off-the-shelf text encoder from CLIP. Dense prompts (masks) are embedded using convolutions and summed element-wise with the image embedding. The mask decoder adeptly maps the image embedding, prompt embeddings and an output token to produce a mask. It utilizes a modified Transformer decoder block with prompt self-attention and cross-attention in two directions (prompt-to-image embedding and vice versa) to update all embeddings. After running two blocks, the image embedding is up-sampled, and an MLP maps the output token to a dynamic linear classifier, which computes the mask foreground probability at each image location.

6.1.1 Application

The Meta AI Research Team offers an HTML Page to run real-time segmentation in browser [51]. Alternatively, it is possible to download the latest pretrained SAM from their GitHub page [52]. There are three versions of the model available with different backbone sizes. From the small ViT-B SAM model at the size of 358MB up to the large ViT-H Model at the size of 2,4GB. This page also contains an example Jupyter Notebooks [53] for creating its own segmentation pipeline. To use SegAnything on your own machine, OpenCV, pycocotools, matplotlib, and the onnxruntime are needed. The SA software and a model checkpoint for segmentation can be downloaded from GitHub.

```

1 from segment_anything import sam_model_registry,
  SamAutomaticMaskGenerator, SamPredictor

```

```
2
3 sam_checkpoint = "sam_vit_b_01ec64.pth"
4 model_type = "vit_b"
5
6 device = "cuda"
7
8 sam = sam_model_registry[model_type](checkpoint=sam_checkpoint)
9 sam.to(device=device)
10
11 mask_generator = SamAutomaticMaskGenerator(
12     model=sam,
13     points_per_side=32,
14     pred_iou_thresh=0.90,
15     stability_score_thresh=0.92,
16     crop_n_layers=2,
17     crop_n_points_downscale_factor=2,
18     min_mask_region_area=100, # Requires open-cv to run post-
19     processing
20 )
21 masks = mask_generator.generate(image)
```

Listing 1: Loading Model Checkpoint and Mask generation.

The code snippet above shows the easiest way to create a mask using own data. At first, a model checkpoint has to be downloaded and set for the mask generator, which is called the `SamAutomaticMaskGenerator`. The instantiation of the `mask_generator` object makes use of the `SamAutomaticMaskGenerator` class and initializes it with several parameters. This parameter can be described as follows:

- `model`: The model used for automatic mask generation.
- `points_per_side`: Number of points per side used in mask generation.
- `pred_iou_thresh`: IoU threshold for accepting mask predictions (0.90 or higher).
- `stability_score_thresh`: Threshold for mask stability score (0.92 or higher).
- `crop_n_layers`: Number of layers on which cropping is applied.
- `crop_n_points_downscale_factor`: Downscale factor for cropping on layers.
- `min_mask_region_area`: Minimum accepted mask region area (requires OpenCV for post-processing).

6.1.2 Fine-Tuning

This pipeline is only suitable for using pre-trained segmentation models as they are. Although this framework displays noteworthy performance in various fields by default, it is not specifically trained for the segmentation of biological images. To refine a pre-existing model for biological image segmentation, fine-tuning is often necessary. This process involves adjusting the model's parameters using a smaller, domain-specific dataset. Fine-tuning is essential to improve the model's suitability and efficacy in addressing the specific requirements of the biological image segmentation task. By refining the model's weights using the specific characteristics and nuances present in the domain-specific dataset, it can accurately

delineate and identify features within biological images. Fine-tuning is critical in this context to optimize the pretrained model's performance and adaptability to the intricacies of biological image analysis. In the case of Segment Anything their exist various sources, how to start a fine-tuning process based on the pretrained models [54] [55].

Fine-tuning a sentiment analysis model is a more complex process than using one off the shelf. A dataset consisting solely of grayscale images and masks is required for the entire fine-tuning process. In the following paragraphs, we will introduce all the necessary steps. The fine-tuning pipeline is based on the MedSAM project [56], which provides a fine-tuned sentiment analysis model for binary segmentation on medical images. A dataset consisting solely of grayscale images and masks is required for the entire fine-tuning process. To effectively segment colony regions while maintaining connected colonies and reducing background noise, it is crucial to select an appropriate thresholding technique. The primary challenge lies in determining a threshold that reduces background noise while preserving the integrity of connected colonies. Figure17 demonstrates the application of a threshold to a colony image.

Figure 17: Applying Threshold on MIX-07.tiff.

Additionally, the input images and masks for this pipeline must be stacked into two TIFF stacks, containing both images and masks separately. To utilize the pipeline for training, the images must be sliced into smaller 256x256-pixel images to fit the training requirements. This procedure is encapsulated in the pipeline and requires no preprocessing steps. The *SegAnything-Helper.ipynb* file contains all the necessary helper scripts for segmentation with SA. SAM is trained using a variety of prompts, including bounding boxes, points, text, and rudimentary masks. These prompts serve as instructions for the model to generate segmentation masks. In order to provide further information to SAM the creation of bounding boxes has to be done. This can be done, using the functionality from the MedSAM repository.

```
1
2 def get_bounding_box(ground_truth_map):
3     # get bounding box from mask
4     y_indices, x_indices = np.where(ground_truth_map > 0)
5     x_min, x_max = np.min(x_indices), np.max(x_indices)
6     y_min, y_max = np.min(y_indices), np.max(y_indices)
7     # add perturbation to bounding box coordinates
8     H, W = ground_truth_map.shape
9     x_min = max(0, x_min - np.random.randint(0, 20))
```

```
10 x_max = min(W, x_max + np.random.randint(0, 20))
11 y_min = max(0, y_min - np.random.randint(0, 20))
12 y_max = min(H, y_max + np.random.randint(0, 20))
13 bbox = [x_min, y_min, x_max, y_max]
14
15 return bbox
```

Listing 2: Creation of Bounding Boxes for train data [56].

During training, this can be achieved by utilising the ground truth map. However, when predicting with a trained model, flexibility becomes necessary, and this will be discussed later. The function necessitates a binary ground truth map as input. Listing 2 shows the function for the creation of bounding boxes. It first identifies the coordinates of the non-zero (positive) elements in the ground truth map, which define the region of interest. Following non-zero elements, the code establishes an initial bounding box by calculating the minimum and maximum x and y coordinates. To introduce randomness and variability, the code injects perturbations. The bounding box coordinates are then modified using random values generated within the range of 0 to 20, making the box larger or smaller. This function is primarily intended for identifying a single bounding box in an image. However, when more than one colony appears in the image, the function results in a larger bounding box covering all the colonies.

The training section of this pipeline is shown in figure 3. The mask decoder parameters are optimized utilizing the Adam optimizer from PyTorch. The DiceCELoss function from the Monai library, which delivers various loss functions, is implemented as the loss function.

```
1 from torch.optim import Adam
2 import monai
3 from tqdm import tqdm
4 from statistics import mean
5 import torch
6 from torch.nn.functional import threshold, normalize
7
8 # Initialize the optimizer and the loss function
9 optimizer = Adam(model.mask_decoder.parameters(), lr=1e-5,
10                  weight_decay=0)
11 #Try DiceFocalLoss, FocalLoss, DiceCELoss
12 seg_loss = monai.losses.DiceCELoss(sigmoid=True, squared_pred=True,
13                                   reduction='mean')
14
15 #Training loop
16 num_epochs = 10
17
18 device = "cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu"
19 model.to(device)
20
21 model.train()
22 for epoch in range(num_epochs):
23     epoch_losses = []
24     for batch in tqdm(train_dataloader):
25         # forward pass
26         outputs = model(pixel_values=batch["pixel_values"].to(device),
```

```
25         input_boxes=batch["input_boxes"].to(device),
26         multimask_output=False)
27
28     # compute loss
29     predicted_masks = outputs.pred_masks.squeeze(1)
30     ground_truth_masks = batch["ground_truth_mask"].float().to(
device)
31     loss = seg_loss(predicted_masks, ground_truth_masks.unsqueeze
(1))
32
33     # backward pass (compute gradients of parameters w.r.t. loss)
34     optimizer.zero_grad()
35     loss.backward()
36
37     # optimize
38     optimizer.step()
39     epoch_losses.append(loss.item())
40
41     print(f'EPOCH: {epoch}')
42     print(f'Mean loss: {mean(epoch_losses)}')
```

Listing 3: Training the SA Mask Decoder.

After completing the training process, the model's dictionary can be stored in a file for future predictions.

Making predictions is more complex than training because it requires the use of Bounding Boxes. Since there is no mask available for prediction, this process has to be generic. Firstly, images for prediction must be saved as a TIFF stack, which is necessary for making predictions. Input images also need to be sliced into patches measuring 256 by 256 pixels. To segment the entire images, the width of the input image - which is originally 960 pixels - is increased to 1024 pixels by adding black pixels. This results in 20 patches per image. At the end, these additional pixels are removed to conform to the input shape of 960 by 1280 pixels.

In the following step, prompts are generated that are essential for predicting the model. Since the images for prediction are not yet segmented, generic bounding boxes need to be created. This can be accomplished by generating a grid of bounding boxes for every patch.

```
1 # Define the size of your array/patch
2 array_size = 256
3
4 # size of grids
5 grid_size = 10
6
7 # Generate the grid points
8 x = np.linspace(0, array_size-1, grid_size)
9 y = np.linspace(0, array_size-1, grid_size)
10
11 # Generate a grid of coordinates
12 xv, yv = np.meshgrid(x, y)
13
14 # Convert the numpy arrays to lists
```

```
15 xv_list = xv.tolist()
16 yv_list = yv.tolist()
17
18 # Combine the x and y coordinates into a list of list of lists
19 input_points = [[[int(x), int(y)] for x, y in zip(x_row, y_row)] for
    x_row, y_row in zip(xv_list, yv_list)]
20
21 #We need to reshape our nxn grid to the expected shape of the
    input_points tensor
22 # (batch_size, point_batch_size, num_points_per_image, 2),
23 # where the last dimension of 2 represents the x and y coordinates of
    each point.
24 #batch_size: The number of images you're processing at once.
25 #point_batch_size: The number of point sets you have for each image.
26 #num_points_per_image: The number of points in each set.
27 input_points = torch.tensor(input_points).view(1, 1, grid_size*
    grid_size, 2)
```

Listing 4: Creation of Boundingboxes for Prediction [55].

Listing 4 demonstrates the creation of bounding boxes for 256-pixel patches. The only parameters required for this task are array size, which describes the patch size, and grid size, which defines the bounding box size. Subsequently, these bounding boxes can be applied to all patches.

6.1.3 Results

Before commencing with fine-tuning, a preliminary testing phase was carried out using the SegAnything model along with readily available pretrained models on their GitHub page. The findings obtained during this preliminary evaluation were remarkable, as demonstrated in figure 18. Although the model was trained on a wide variety of images, most of which were not biological images, the model promise to be a good starting point for further modification.

Figure 18: Testing SAM on Colony Images.

With the presented fine-tuning pipeline the SAM model was trained over 200 epochs. An extract of the findings is depicted in figure 19.

Figure 19: Evaluation of Accuracy and IoU of the first 3 validation images.

Over the entire testing dataset, SegAnything achieves an accuracy of 0.90 and an intersection over union (IoU) of 0.75. These values fall short of the required performance for this task. However, the figure provides insight into the insufficiency of this performance. Figure 19 demonstrates the varying segmentation results of 256 x 256 pixel patches. To plot the disparity between the actual values and predictions, the absolute difference is utilised. Some patches showcase exceptional segmentation, while others classify almost the entire patch as a colony. This observation is related to the applied image threshold, which aids in enhancing background segmentation. As shown in figure 17, this phenomenon is evident, where the constant threshold causes fusion between the background and colony in the image's right corner.

After implementing several other image preprocessing techniques, such as threshold optimization and the use of adaptive thresholding based on local characteristics, there was no improvement in performance.

In conclusion, SegAnything is a versatile segmentation tool that performs well in various applications, as demonstrated by the MedSam project [56]. However, in this specific use case

of colony image segmentation, fine-tuning the pipeline did not yield satisfactory results. One possible explanation is that the images are not suitable for this network. Additionally, further modifications to the SegAnything model may be necessary for this task to be performed accurately. The recently presented CellSAM project [57] addresses this further fine-tuning and could be explored for this task in the future.

6.2 DeLTA 2.0

DeLTA 2.0 (Deep Learning for Time-lapse Analysis) is a deep learning-powered image processing pipeline designed for the segmentation and tracking of cells in time-lapse microscopy video sequences [42]. This software was developed by the Dunlop Lab, a component of the Department of Biomedical Engineering at Boston University, Massachusetts. It is developing a deep learning segmentation pipeline for 2D input data, providing the potential for tracking. DeLTA 2.0 is a U-Net derived program available on both Central Processing Unit (CPU) and Graphics Processing Unit (GPU), programmed using TensorFlow 2 [58]. As this project remains active, the software developer responds promptly if assistance is required. Additionally, they furnish various resources on how to utilise DeLTA 2.0 software to establish custom segmentation networks. Consequentially, they offer diverse scripts for handling training and test data, forming weight maps or retraining the network. Basic skills in neural networks and Python programming are required. Although DeLTA 2.0 is still in development and the possibility of integrating a Graphical User Interface (GUI) to correct segmentation and tracking errors is being evaluated, currently DeLTA 2.0 does not provide a GUI.

DeLTA 2.0: A deep learning pipeline for quantifying single-cell spatial and temporal dynamics, published in 2022, presents the second iteration of DeLTA, a pure Python workflow for analysing images of single cells on two-dimensional surfaces. While DeLTA 2.0 remains capable of analyzing mother-machine images, it now has the added ability to process two-dimensional images. The architecture and pipeline of the original version were retained in DeLTA 2.0, with enhancements introduced. Figure 20 depicts DeLTA 2.0.

Figure 20: DeLTA 2.0 (A) DeLTA 2.0 pipeline. (B) Segmentation U-Net. (C) Tracking U-Net. (D) Lineage reconstruction [42].

While the initial version of DeLTA necessitated pre- and post-processing in Matlab, DeLTA 2.0 has shifted to being exclusively Python-based. Additional enhancements entail the potential to utilize the Bio-Formats toolbox for Python. DeLTA 2.0 accepts a range of input image sizes, and crops larger images into smaller windows for segmentation before stitching the results together. In order to prevent overfitting, blurring and Gaussian noise addition data augmentation methods have been integrated with the existing ones.

The weight maps utilised in DeLTA 2.0's loss function were customised to enhance rod-shaped bacteria segmentation by increasing the weightage for cell centres and borders.

The function that generates weight maps for new training data from the ground truth has been implemented. The segmentation model underwent training for 500 epochs with 300 steps and a batch size of 1. For further information a documentation is available [59].

DeLTA 2.0's segmentation abilities have a diverse range of applications. Past projects [60] [61] have demonstrated its effectiveness in segmenting individual cells. Moreover, these studies have illustrated the potential benefits of custom data training in improving segmentation quality when applied to DeLTA 2.0, in comparison to the use of a pre-trained model.

To use this software for colony segmentation, a specific retraining process is necessary. Nevertheless, incorporating it into the developed workflow could enhance the workflow's generality and enable future project reuse, even if the software is incapable of colony segmentation.

6.2.1 Application

Besides retraining DeLTA 2.0 offers a pretrained model for cell segmentation, which can be the first start for using this image pipeline for bio images.

The initial phase of utilizing DeLTA involves configuring the delta pipeline. JSON files are utilized to store the configurations for running DeLTA 2.0. The configuration file facilitates the parameterization of operations within the modules. A description of all parameters can be found in the DeLTA 2.0 documentation [59]. For this project, the configuration file has been modified to suit the specific use-case by adjusting the directory paths.

To develop a full DeLTA segmentation model, it is imperative to include weight maps in the training data. Weight maps are particularly useful in situations where emphasis or de-emphasis of specific objects or regions within images is required during the training process. By assigning varying weights to pixels based on their importance, the model can be guided to focus on specific details. Accurate outlining of objects or instances within an image is vital in image segmentation tasks. Though they may be optional for training, their use leads to better outlining of the instances. Weight maps can be calculated by using binary masks of an image.

An example weight map of an image and mask pertaining to our application is shown in the figure 21 below.

Figure 21: Example Data for DeLTA: image (left), mask(middle), weight map (right).

To use the DeLTA model for the segmentation process, it is mostly necessary to adapt the model for the own use case. This can be done by retrain the whole network with custom images or training the existing pretrained delta model. DeLTA 2.0 offers a prepared script to retrain the segmentation model.

```
1 """
2 This script trains the cell segmentation U-Net
3
4 @author: jblugagne
5 @edited: b,gericke,rschlonsak
6
7 """
8 import os
9 import glob
10 import sys
11 import warnings
12 sys.path.append('../delta-dev')
13
14 warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
15 from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import ModelCheckpoint, EarlyStopping
16
17 from delta.utilities import cfg
18 from delta.model import unet_seg
19 from delta.data import trainGenerator_seg
20 # Load config:
21 cfg.load_config('config_coloy.json')
22
23 # Files:
24 training_set = os.path.abspath(cfg.training_set_seg)
25 savefile = os.path.abspath(cfg.model_file_seg)
26
27 # Training parameters:
28 batch_size = 1
29 epochs = 600
30 steps_per_epoch = 300
31 patience = 50
32
33 # Data generator parameters:
34 data_gen_args = dict(
```

```
35     rotation=2,
36     rotations_90d=True,
37     zoom=0.15,
38     horizontal_flip=True,
39     vertical_flip=True,
40     illumination_voodoo=True,
41     gaussian_noise=0.03,
42     gaussian_blur=1,
43 )
44 # Generator init:
45 myGene = trainGenerator_seg(
46     batch_size,
47     os.path.abspath(os.path.join(training_set, "img")),
48     os.path.abspath(os.path.join(training_set, "seg")),
49     os.path.abspath(os.path.join(training_set, "wei")),
50     augment_params=data_gen_args,
51     target_size=cfg.target_size_seg,
52     crop_windows=cfg.crop_windows,
53 )
54 myGene
55
56 model = unet_seg(input_size=cfg.target_size_seg + (1,))
57 model.summary()
58
59 model_checkpoint = ModelCheckpoint(
60     savefile, monitor="loss", verbose=2, save_best_only=True
61 )
62 early_stopping = EarlyStopping(monitor="loss", mode="min", verbose=2,
63     patience=patience)
64
65 history = model.fit(
66     myGene,
67     steps_per_epoch=steps_per_epoch,
68     epochs=epochs,
69     callbacks=[model_checkpoint, early_stopping],
70 )
```

Listing 5: Script for retraining DeLTA 2.0.

Using the script from listing 5 and the configuration it is possible to retrain a delta model for segmentation for different use-cases.

For the prediction and evaluation of a trained model, DeLTA provides a flexible script. It was necessary to modify the script to work with an image directory to segment all TIFF images in an input directory, considering the script's interpretation of evaluation movies.

```
1 import os
2 import glob
3
4 import numpy as np
5 from pathlib import Path
6
```

```
7 from delta.data import saveResult_seg, predictGenerator_seg,
  postprocess, readreshape
8 from delta.model import unet_seg
9 import delta.utilities as utils
10 from delta.utilities import cfg
11
12 cfg.load_config('config_colony.json')
13
14 model = unet_seg(input_size=cfg.target_size_seg + (1,))
15 model.load_weights(cfg.model_file_seg)
16
17 # Input image sequence (change to whatever images sequence you want
  to evaluate):
18 inputs_folder = str("data/test/imgs")
19
20 # Outputs folder:
21 outputs_folder = os.path.join((inputs_folder), "segmentation")
22 if not os.path.exists(outputs_folder):
23     os.makedirs(outputs_folder)
24
25 # Get absolute path, otherwise delta/data.py readreshape()-cv2.imread
  () can't find file
26 outputs_folder = os.path.abspath(outputs_folder)
27 inputs_folder = os.path.abspath(inputs_folder)
28
29 # List files in inputs folder:
30 unprocessed = sorted(
31     glob.glob(inputs_folder + "/*.tiff")
32 )
33
34 # Process
35 while unprocessed:
36     # Pop out filenames
37     ps = min(4096, len(unprocessed)) # 4096 at a time
38     to_process = unprocessed[0:ps]
39     del unprocessed[0:ps]
40
41     # Input data generator:
42     predGene = predictGenerator_seg(
43         inputs_folder,
44         files_list=to_process,
45         target_size=cfg.target_size_seg,
46         crop=cfg.crop_windows,
47     )
48
49     # mother machine: Don't crop images into windows
50     if not cfg.crop_windows:
51         # Predictions:
52         results = model.predict(predGene, verbose=1)[: , : , : , 0]
53
54     # 2D: Cut into overlapping windows
```

```
55     else:
56         img = readreshape(
57             os.path.join(inputs_folder, to_process[0]),
58             target_size=config.target_size_seg,
59             crop=True,
60         )
61         # Create array to store predictions
62         results = np.zeros((len(to_process), img.shape[0], img.shape
63 [1], 1))
64         # Crop, segment, stitch and store predictions in results
65         for i in range(len(to_process)):
66             # Crop each frame into overlapping windows:
67             windows, loc_y, loc_x = utils.create_windows(
68                 next(predGene)[0, :, :], target_size=config.
69 target_size_seg
70             )
71             # We have to play around with tensor dimensions to
72 conform to
73 # tensorflow's functions:
74 windows = windows[:, :, :, np.newaxis]
75 # Predictions:
76 pred = model.predict(windows, verbose=1, steps=windows.
77 shape[0])
78 # Stich prediction frames back together:
79 pred = utils.stitch_pic(pred[:, :, :, 0], loc_y, loc_x)
80 pred = pred[np.newaxis, :, :, np.newaxis] # Mess around
81 with dims
82
83         results[i] = pred
84
85         # Post process results (binarize + light morphology-based
86 cleaning):
87         results = postprocess(results, crop=config.crop_windows)
88
89         # Save to disk:
90         saveResult_seg(outputs_folder, results, files_list=to_process)
```

Listing 6: Script for predicting with DeLTA 2.0.

The code listed in 6 is suitable for producing validation predictions to assess the metrics of a trained model. DeLTA functionalities can be employed to manage the training process metrics. These scripts can equip users to train and utilise a trained model on bespoke data.

6.2.2 Results

For the purpose of performance evaluation, we trained the delta model for 200 epochs using previously computed weight maps. The best model was saved based on minimal loss. The validation set was identical to the one used for SegAnything fine-tuning.

Figure 22: Evaluation of Accuracy and IoU of the first 3 validation images.

The evaluation of the first three validation images is shown in figure 22. The average accuracy across all images was 0.95 and the IoU was 0.88, which is similarly impressive. The summary indicates a strong performance on the validation set. These results denote a close alignment between the predicted segmentation masks and their ground truth counterparts, as evidenced by the Intersection over Union score. This result shows promise regarding the model's efficacy in capturing the objects of interest in the images.

For further information a zoomed in picture is plotted in figure 23.

Figure 23: Enhanced Detail: Close-up View of the Mask for 'MIX-11.tiff.

Figure 23 illustrates a significant finding: the model has a main focus on breaking down colonies into smaller sub-sections, which is associated with the application of weight maps. The algorithm seems to strive for enhancing this feature, even if the weight maps generated do not inherently suggest dividing colonies into sub-sections.

This suggests that the model can learn and adapt its segmentation strategy according to the given weight maps. Weight maps are meant to guide the segmentation process by focusing on specific areas of interest. Although weight maps may not explicitly suggest the need for sub-partitioning, the model recognises the potential advantages of such divisions and strives to improve its performance accordingly.

6.3 Omnipose

Omnipose [62] represents a potent tool for cell segmentation, grounded on the U-Net architecture, which is extensively employed within the scientific realm. It achieves remarkable precision in the segmentation of cells featuring varied morphologies and sourced from diverse imaging modalities, encompassing microscopy images, fluorescence images, and electron microscopy images. Omnipose proves to be beneficial for cell segmentation in intricate or noisy images, such as those consisting of mixed cultures, antibiotic-treated cells, and cells with elongated or branched morphologies. This segmentation tool operates on the framework of Cellpose [63] which emerged in 2020. Cellpose is a 2D algorithm for cell segmentation, trained on diverse cell types and fluorescence images. Omnipose includes numerous enhancements over Cellpose. The unprecedented segmentation accuracy is showcased, especially in relation to bacterial cells. The accuracy of Omnipose significantly surpasses that of Cellpose, even when using the same training dataset. The distinction is attributed to Omnipose's exclusive network outputs, like boundary, distance, and flow, alongside advancements to the training framework [62].

The distinct outputs of Omnipose’s network, which include boundary, distance, and flow, enhance its segmentation performance compared to Cellpose. The boundary output provides a probability map of cell boundaries, resulting in more precise delineation of cell boundaries. The distance output shows the distance from each pixel to the closest cell boundary, enabling finer thresholding for cell mask generation. The gradient of the distance field defines the flow output, which offers further insights into the spatial arrangement of cells.

Besides the network outputs, Omnipose’s performance is boosted by various enhancements to its training framework, such as bespoke loss functions, an alternative optimiser (RAdam [64]) and image augmentations. These modifications optimise the training process and improve the network’s capacity to learn and apply generalisations to varied cellular morphologies.

The unique network outputs and enhancements to the training framework in Omnipose result in unparalleled segmentation accuracy for a wide array of cell types and imaging modalities.

6.3.1 Application

Due to its advanced cell segmentation performance, it should be feasible to utilise this tool for colony image segmentation.

To segment the colony images using this software, the Omnipose GitHub repository offers multiple available scripts [65]. The initial stage in using Omnipose for segmentation involves selecting a segmentation model. Omnipose offers pre-trained models that can be utilised by users for their cell segmentation tasks. These pre-trained models have undergone training on varied datasets and may be used without needing extra training. Examples of pre-trained models available in Omnipose include fluorescence image-trained models and those for non-bacterial subjects, for example, the *Caenorhabditis elegans* nematode. These models have been fine-tuned to achieve precise segmentation outcomes for distinct imaging modalities and cell categories.

```
1 ['bact_phase_omni',
2  'bact_fluor_omni',
3  'worm_omni',
4  'worm_bact_omni',
5  'worm_high_res_omni',
6  'cyto2_omni',
7  'plant_omni',
8  'bact_phase_cp',
9  'bact_fluor_cp',
10 'plant_cp',
11 'worm_cp',
12 'cyto',
13 'nuclei',
14 'cyto2']
```

Listing 7: Omnipose Pretrained Models.

Listing 7 offers a summary of the pre-trained models. Once selecting the apt segmentation model, the model is initiated, and a small number of hyperparameters are shown, as demonstrated in listing 8.

```
1 model_name = 'bact_phase_omni'
2 model = models.CellposeModel(gpu=use_GPU, model_type=model_name)
```

```
3 chans = [0,0] #this means segment based on first channel, no second
  channel
4 n = [-3] # make a list of integers to select which images you want to
  segment
5 n = range(nimg) # or just segment them all
6
7 # define parameters
8 mask_threshold = -1
9 verbose = 0 # turn on if you want to see more output
10 use_gpu = use_GPU #defined above
11 transparency = True # transparency in flow output
12 rescale=None # give this a number if you need to upscale or downscale
  your images
13 omni = True # we can turn off Omnipose mask reconstruction, not
  advised
14 flow_threshold = 0 # default is .4, but only needed if there are
  spurious masks to clean up; slows down output
15 resample = True # whether or not to run dynamics on rescaled grid or
  original grid
16 cluster=True # use DBSCAN clustering
17 tile = True # break up image into smaller parts then stitch together
18 affinity_seg = 1 #new feature, stay tuned...
19
20 masks, flows, styles = model.eval([imgs[i] for i in n],
21                                   channels=chans,
22                                   rescale=rescale,
23                                   mask_threshold=mask_threshold,
24                                   transparency=transparency,
25                                   flow_threshold=flow_threshold,
26                                   omni=omni,
27                                   cluster=cluster,
28                                   resample=resample,
29                                   verbose=verbose,
30                                   affinity_seg=affinity_seg,
31                                   tile=tile)
```

Listing 8: Using Omnipose for prediction.

All selectable hyperparameters are specified in the code snippet above. These parameters determine how the cell segmentation model processes input images, including channel selection, post-processing, clustering, and more. The values for these parameters can have a significant impact on the quality and characteristics of the segmentation results.

The segmentation output of Omnipose consists of several components, including boundary, distance, and flow maps, which provide detailed information about the segmented cells. The boundary map is a probability map that indicates the likelihood of each pixel belonging to a cell boundary. It allows for more accurate delineation of cell boundaries, enabling precise segmentation of individual cells.

The distance map represents the distance from each pixel to the nearest cell boundary. It provides information about the spatial organization of cells and can be used for thresholding to generate cell masks with high precision.

The flow map, defined by the gradient of the distance field, provides additional information about the connectivity and shape of cells. It captures the direction and magnitude of the flow of pixels towards the cell boundaries, aiding in the identification and characterization of cell structures.

Figure 24: Omnipose segmentation output [66].

Figure 24 shows the output from listing 8 consisting of the predicted outline, the masks, and the predicted flow field.

6.3.2 Results

To evaluate the performance of the Omnipose framework, we executed tests on the data using each pretrained model and adjusting the hyperparameters. The segmentation procedure was conducted on various morphological subtypes, ranging from images that display a specific subtype to those that display a mixture.

Figure 25 illustrates the segmentation results obtained using the Omnipose framework on a series of colony images. In these images, we experimented with both single subtype and mixed subtype colonies to assess the framework's performance. Unfortunately, the results were far from satisfactory. Despite the framework's success in accurately segmenting individual cells, it faces significant challenges when it comes to colony segmentation.

Figure 25: Omnipose output on Colony images.

Colony segmentation is a crucial task in various scientific and industrial applications, such as microbiology and biotechnology, where understanding the dynamics and characteristics of entire colonies is essential. However, our experiments indicate that the existing models provided by the Omnipose framework do not meet the requirements for accurate colony segmentation.

The performance can be evaluated using metrics on the validation images. The first three images from the validation set are displayed in figure 26. The average Intersection over Union (IoU) and accuracy are 0.02 and 0.60, respectively.

Figure 26: Evaluation of Accuracy and IoU of the first 3 validation images.

It is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of the Omnipose framework, especially when it comes to colony segmentation. While it excels in many aspects of cell segmentation, the intricacies of colonies present unique challenges. However, recognizing these limitations is the first step toward finding solutions. This acknowledgment leads us to explore potential avenues for improvement. One promising approach is to consider retraining the Omnipose framework to specifically address the task of colony segmentation. The framework provides a valuable foundation with its deep learning architecture and powerful image analysis capabilities. By fine-tuning and retraining the existing models, it exists the opportunity to adapt the framework to the complexities of colonies.

6.4 Conclusion

In this section 3 different segmentation tools were investigated. The metrics for all tools are presented in table 1.

The table presents the outcomes of comparing tools objectively. In this task, the DeLTA 2.0 model performed better than its counterparts. Following the retraining of DeLTA 2.0 for colony segmentation, a model was obtained that gave very satisfactory results in image segmentation. Due to variations in performance of Segment Anything in specific image patches, DeLTA 2.0 is the optimal solution for the segmentation component of the workflow.

Metrics	DeLTA 2.0	Segment Anything	Omnipose
Accuracy	0.95	0.90	0.60
Intersection over Union (IoU)	0.88	0.75	0.02

Table 1: Comparison of Segmentation Tool Performance.

By addressing these issues, the Segment Anything model could become a more effective solution for this task.

7 Classifier

In this chapter, we will present the functional classification method used in this project, based on the obtained images and generated masks. The data presents a challenge due to the significant class imbalance observed. One class has only 94 samples, while the other has approximately 1200 samples. This imbalance complicates the distinction of specific mutants, and can negatively affect classifier training, leading to biased performance and inaccurate predictions, particularly for the minority class.

To tackle these challenges and promote a more robust classification process, categorizing colonies into three types (smooth, wrinkly, and mixed) seems to be a strategic approach. With further samples, this classification strategy can be adapted to meet the requirements for discriminating between all 5 mutants and mixed colonies. This consolidation of similar characteristics into broader categories may redress the imbalance and enhance the classifier's generalisation across all categories. The colony types are presented in figure 27.

Figure 27: Colony Types: smooth (wild type) (left), wrinkly spreader (middle), mix (right).

7.1 Preprocessing

The figure shows already extracted colonies for training the classifier. To obtain this single colony images a few steps are needed.

The first step that is needed is to extract the colony instances from the mask to obtain the ROI from the mask in the second step. This process is shown in figure 28.

Figure 28: ROI Extraction with the help of a binary mask.

To find the contours of each colony in the binary mask special images functions can be used. Around this contours a bounding box can be created as shown in figure 28. This bounding box can be applied to the image to obtain the ROI as a image. This image can contain other colony parts, that would distort the classification results. To solve this problem, the part of the instance images that is not belonging to the colony in focus, must be colored black, to ensure the right colony gets classified in the further process. The result of this operation is shown in figure 29.

Figure 29: ROI Processing: unprocessed ROI (left) , processed ROI (right).

The contours of a colony can be technically employed to delineate a clear Region of Interest (ROI), ensuring the extraction of a specific area encompassing only one colony. The whole function for this ROI extraction is shown in listing 9.

```
1 def extract_and_save_rois(image_folder, mask_folder, output_folder):
2     # Check if the output folder exists, create it if it doesn't
3     if not os.path.exists(output_folder):
4         os.makedirs(output_folder)
5
6     # Iterate through the files in the image folder
7     for image_filename in os.listdir(image_folder):
8         if image_filename.endswith('.tif') or image_filename.endswith
9         ('.tiff'):
10            # Create the filename for the mask
11            mask_filename = os.path.join(mask_folder, image_filename)
12
13            # Check if the mask file exists
14            if os.path.isfile(mask_filename):
15                # Load the image
16                image = cv2.imread(os.path.join(image_folder,
17                image_filename), cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)
18
19                # Load the mask
20                mask = cv2.imread(mask_filename, cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED
21                )
22
23                # Find the contours of the ROIs
24                contours, _ = cv2.findContours(mask, cv2.
25                RETR_EXTERNAL, cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)
26
27                # Remove the .tif or .tiff extension from
28                image_filename
29                image_name_without_extension = os.path.splitext(
30                image_filename)[0]
31
32                # Iterate through the contours and save the ROIs
33                for i, contour in enumerate(contours):
34                    x, y, w, h = cv2.boundingRect(contour)
35
36                    # Create the ROI as a copy of the original image
37                    roi = image[y:y+h, x:x+w]
38
39                    # Create a binary mask for the region outside the
40                    contour
41                    mask_roi = np.zeros((h, w), dtype=np.uint8)
42                    cv2.drawContours(mask_roi, [contour - (x, y)], 0,
43                    255, thickness=cv2.FILLED)
44
45                    # Apply the binary mask to make the region
46                    outside the contour black
47                    roi = cv2.bitwise_and(roi, roi, mask=mask_roi)
48
49
```

```
40         # Create the filename with an instance identifier
41         and number
42         output_filename = os.path.join(output_folder, f"{
43         image_name_without_extension}_instance_{i}.tif")
44         cv2.imwrite(output_filename, roi)
45
46 # Use the function to extract and save ROIs
47 image_folder = 'binary_seg_data/train/normalized_images'
48 mask_folder = 'binary_seg_data/train/masks'
49 output_folder = 'classification/all'
50
51 extract_and_save_rois(image_folder, mask_folder, output_folder)
52 print("done")
```

Listing 9: ROI Extraction function.

The OpenCV image library provides the capability to identify contours in images. For generating output images, these contours can be drawn onto a black image. To ensure that an image only includes one colony, the image data is solely applied to the space enclosed by the contour.

To prepare the generated instance images for processing, it is essential to resize them all to a uniform size. In order to facilitate classification, we resize each image to a size of 512 x 512 pixels. Subsequent alterations can be made through the use of data transformations within the neural networks during both training and prediction.

After all images are resized, it is needed to store them class wise in directories for training, validation and testing. The data structure for this process is shown in the figure 30 below.

Figure 30: Directory structure of data for classification.

As not all images contain a single colony type, the colony instances from the mixed images required manual sorting into their respective subfolders. The mixed images are the only data that contain all three colony types simultaneously.

Because of this, the mix class have only around 200 samples against up to 2000 samples for the other classes. To improve the performance of the classifier for predicting mix colonies, it is necessary to improve the data for this type. This can be done by data augmentation which is shown in listing 10.

```
1 # Function for data augmentation (rotation) on TIFF files
2 def augment_images_in_folder(input_folder, output_folder):
3     # Create the output folder if it doesn't exist
4     if not os.path.exists(output_folder):
5         os.makedirs(output_folder)
6
7     # Define the rotation angles
8     rotation_angles = [90, 180, 270]
9
10    # Iterate through TIFF files in the input folder
11    for filename in os.listdir(input_folder):
12        if filename.endswith(('.tif', '.tiff')):
13            # Load the TIFF image
14            image = cv2.imread(os.path.join(input_folder, filename),
15                                cv2.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)
16
17            # Apply data augmentation (rotation) and save the images
18            for angle in rotation_angles:
19                rotated_image = perform_augmentation(image, angle)
20                output_filename = os.path.splitext(filename)[0] + f'
21                _rotated_{angle}.tif'
22                output_path = os.path.join(output_folder,
23                    output_filename)
24                cv2.imwrite(output_path, rotated_image)
25
26    # Function to perform data augmentation (rotation)
27    def perform_augmentation(image, angle):
28        # Rotate the image by the specified angle
29        if angle == 90:
30            rotated_image = cv2.rotate(image, cv2.ROTATE_90_CLOCKWISE)
31        elif angle == 180:
32            rotated_image = cv2.rotate(image, cv2.ROTATE_180)
33        elif angle == 270:
34            rotated_image = cv2.rotate(image, cv2.
35            ROTATE_90_COUNTERCLOCKWISE)
36        else:
37            rotated_image = image # No rotation
38
39        return rotated_image
```

Listing 10: Data Augmentation for colony images.

In this scenario, the images are only rotated by angles of 90, 180, and 270 degrees to obtain the colony's structure, as opposed to operations like reflection. Consequently, roughly 600 samples are generated for the mixed class. To enhance class balance by eliminating arbitrary samples from the other class, a distinct function was implemented.

The next step is to split the data into datasets for training, validation, and testing. There fore a special function was implemented, that is shown in listing 11.

```
1 # Function to split a dataset into train, validation, and test sets
2 def split_dataset(input_folder, output_folder, train_ratio=0.7,
3     val_ratio=0.15, test_ratio=0.15):
```

```
3 # Create the output folders if they don't exist
4 train_folder = os.path.join(output_folder, "train")
5 val_folder = os.path.join(output_folder, "val")
6 test_folder = os.path.join(output_folder, "test")
7
8 for folder in [train_folder, val_folder, test_folder]:
9     if not os.path.exists(folder):
10         os.makedirs(folder)
11
12 # Iterate through class folders in the input folder
13 for class_folder in os.listdir(input_folder):
14     class_path = os.path.join(input_folder, class_folder)
15
16     # Create corresponding class subfolders in train, validation,
17     # and test folders
18     train_class_folder = os.path.join(train_folder, class_folder)
19     val_class_folder = os.path.join(val_folder, class_folder)
20     test_class_folder = os.path.join(test_folder, class_folder)
21
22     for folder in [train_class_folder, val_class_folder,
23 test_class_folder]:
24         if not os.path.exists(folder):
25             os.makedirs(folder)
26
27         # List all image files in the class folder
28         image_files = [f for f in os.listdir(class_path) if f.lower()
29 .endswith(('.tif', '.tiff'))]
30
31         # Shuffle the image files to randomize the split
32         random.shuffle(image_files)
33
34         # Calculate the split indices
35         num_images = len(image_files)
36         num_train = int(train_ratio * num_images)
37         num_val = int(val_ratio * num_images)
38
39         # Assign images to the corresponding sets
40         train_images = image_files[:num_train]
41         val_images = image_files[num_train:num_train + num_val]
42         test_images = image_files[num_train + num_val:]
43
44         # Copy images to their respective folders
45         for image in train_images:
46             src = os.path.join(class_path, image)
47             dst = os.path.join(train_class_folder, image)
48             shutil.copy(src, dst)
49
50         for image in val_images:
51             src = os.path.join(class_path, image)
52             dst = os.path.join(val_class_folder, image)
53             shutil.copy(src, dst)
```

```
51
52     for image in test_images:
53         src = os.path.join(class_path, image)
54         dst = os.path.join(test_class_folder, image)
55         shutil.copy(src, dst)
```

Listing 11: Splitting data into subsets.

For this process, a division of 70% for training, 15% each for validation and testing is employed. The training, validation and testing folders are created following the same subfolder structure as illustrated in figure 30.

7.2 Training

After the data preparation stage, a model can be trained. We have selected ResNet, which was introduced in Chapter 4.3, for this purpose. ResNet-50 was chosen as a suitable starting point for classification based on previous research on segmentation and classification workflows [67] [68].

The utilization of the PyTorch data-loader serves as a valuable asset for data-loading tasks. The classification of images is automatically inferred from the respective folder names, creating a framework that enables the application of the training function in listing 12. This structure ensures the readiness of our data for future classification assignments, offering a seamless and standardized approach for handling diverse classification tasks.

```
1 # Define data transformations
2 data_transforms = {
3     'train': transforms.Compose([
4         transforms.RandomResizedCrop(224),
5         transforms.RandomHorizontalFlip(),
6         transforms.ToTensor(),
7         transforms.Normalize([0.485, 0.456, 0.406], [0.229, 0.224,
8         0.225])
9     ]),
10    'val': transforms.Compose([
11        transforms.Resize(256),
12        transforms.CenterCrop(224),
13        transforms.ToTensor(),
14        transforms.Normalize([0.485, 0.456, 0.406], [0.229, 0.224,
15        0.225])
16    ]),
17 }
18 # Define dataset directories
19 data_dir = 'classification' # Update with your dataset folder
20 image_datasets = {x: datasets.ImageFolder(os.path.join(data_dir, x),
21     data_transforms[x])
22     for x in ['train', 'val']}
23 dataloaders = {x: DataLoader(image_datasets[x], batch_size=3, shuffle
24     =True, num_workers=0)
25     for x in ['train', 'val']}
26 # Access the class-to-index mapping
```

```
24 class_to_idx = image_datasets['train'].class_to_idx
25
26 # Reverse the dictionary to get index-to-class mapping
27 idx_to_class = {v: k for k, v in class_to_idx.items()}
28
29 # Get the class names
30 class_names = [idx_to_class[i] for i in range(len(class_to_idx))]
31 # Print the class names and their corresponding indices
32 for i, class_name in enumerate(class_names):
33     print(f"Class {i}: {class_name}")
34
35 # Load the pre-trained ResNet-50 model
36 base_model = models.resnet50(pretrained=True)
37
38 # Modify the final classification layer for your number of classes
39 num_classes = 3 # Replace with your number of classes
40 num_features = base_model.fc.in_features
41 base_model.fc = nn.Linear(num_features, num_classes)
42
43 # Define the loss function and optimizer
44 criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()
45 optimizer = optim.Adam(base_model.parameters(), lr=0.001)
46
47 # Training loop
48 def train_model(model, dataloaders, criterion, optimizer, num_epochs
49 =1):
50     device = torch.device("cuda:0" if torch.cuda.is_available() else
51 "cpu")
52     model = model.to(device)
53
54     best_val_acc = 0.0
55     best_model_weights = model.state_dict()
56
57     for epoch in range(num_epochs):
58         for phase in ['train', 'val']:
59             if phase == 'train':
60                 model.train()
61             else:
62                 model.eval()
63
64             running_loss = 0.0
65             running_corrects = 0
66
67             # Wrap the dataloaders with tqdm for progress bars
68             data_loader = tqdm(dataloaders[phase], total=len(
69 dataloaders[phase]), leave=True)
70             for inputs, labels in data_loader:
71                 inputs = inputs.to(device)
72                 labels = labels.to(device)
73
74                 optimizer.zero_grad()
```

```
72
73         with torch.set_grad_enabled(phase == 'train'):
74             outputs = model(inputs)
75             _, preds = torch.max(outputs, 1)
76             loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
77
78             if phase == 'train':
79                 loss.backward()
80                 optimizer.step()
81
82             running_loss += loss.item() * inputs.size(0)
83             running_correcets += torch.sum(preds == labels.data)
84
85         epoch_loss = running_loss / len(dataloaders[phase].
dataset)
86         epoch_acc = running_correcets.double() / len(dataloaders[
phase].dataset)
87
88         print(f'Epoch {epoch} {phase} Loss: {epoch_loss:.4f} Acc:
{epoch_acc:.4f}')
89         # Save the best model based on validation accuracy
90         if phase == 'val' and epoch_acc.item() > best_val_acc:
91             best_val_acc = epoch_acc.item()
92             best_model_weights = model.state_dict()
93         # Save the best model weights to a file
94         torch.save(best_model_weights, 'models/classification/
best_model10epochs.pth')
```

Listing 12: Training function for Classification with ResNet 50.

During the training process, the model is optimized by implementing the Cross-Entropy Loss function, which is considered a fundamental component in the field of machine and deep learning, particularly for classification tasks. This type of loss function is also known as the logarithmic loss or simply as Cross-Entropy, and it is important due to its ability to precisely quantify the discrepancy between the predicted probability distribution of class labels and the genuine (target) probability distribution. As the training progresses, it is crucial to determine the most suitable model configuration. This is achieved through a model selection process based on the model's performance on a separate validation dataset. The best model is selected based on a simple criterion of exhibiting the highest accuracy on the validation dataset.

This strategy guarantees that the model chosen performs well in generating precise predictions, while simultaneously maintaining a significant level of trust in these predictions. By obtaining optimum accuracy in the validation dataset, this model exhibits its potential to 'generalize' to data that has not been viewed before, further strengthening confidence in its capabilities.

7.3 Results

The model has undergone 100 epochs of training without any further optimizations. Figure 31 illustrates the accuracy graph, which displays an intriguing pattern.

A remarkable observation is the significant fluctuation in the validation loss. This variation could be attributed to the relatively small size of the validation set. To address this problem, a potential avenue for future research would be to train the network on a more extensive dataset. This stage has the potential to enhance the stability and dependability of the model's performance evaluations throughout the validation process.

Figure 31: Accuracy Graph over 100 epochs training.

Nonetheless, the trained network achieved an accuracy of 0.96, after which it was saved and tested on an unfamiliar test set. The model attained an accuracy of 0.9551 over the course of this test set, which is relatively commendable.

Table 2: Classification Report.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
mix	0.85	0.88	0.87
smooth (wild type)	0.97	0.98	0.97
wrinkly	0.98	0.96	0.97
average	0.93	0.94	0.93

While the model's performance is indeed commendable, a closer examination of the results can give more insights.

Table 2 displays precision, recall, and F1-scores for each class.

The model demonstrates high performance for "smooth" and "wrinkly" colonies, with similar values. Both "smooth" and "wrinkly" have excellent precision, at 0.97 and 0.98, respectively, and strong recall, at 0.98 and 0.96. This implies consistent performance for these classes.

However, differences in performance are observed when examining the "mix" colonies. The precision for such colonies is substantially lower at 0.85 in comparison to the other classes.

This indicates that, when the model predicts a colony as "mix," it is correct 85% of the time, but it produces more false positives. The recall for "mix" colonies is also lower, which shows that the model fails to identify a proportion of actual "mix" colonies.

The difference in precision and recall for "mix" colonies has an impact on the F1-score, which represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Although the F1-score for "mix" colonies is still respectable at 0.87, it is lower compared to the other categories.

The poor performance of the "mix" colonies can be attributed to the lack of available images. The "mix" colonies constitute approximately 3% of the total provided data, which has been augmented and pruned later. With augmentation, the entire dataset for colony classification comprises 500 samples per class, that has been divided for training, testing, and validation purposes.

In the future, the datasets need to be updated to improve the model and test its performance on real world data. This possible data collection could be done with the help of special data augmentation [69]. An idea would be to build mixed colonies by generate them artificial based on colony instances of different strains. However, this classifier can be utilised for upcoming projects to differentiate all wrinkly spreader mutants.

8 Workflow

After introducing essential technologies for segmenting and classifying, the two parts should be integrated into an appropriate workflow. Formulating a segmentation and classification workflow is a challenging task that demands meticulous planning and execution, taking into account various critical factors. The implemented workflow is available from the gitlab project [70] and is described in this chapter.

In this project, the workflow should be practical for biologists with basic computing knowledge, as well as for more experienced scientists who will maintain the workflow.

Figure 32: Overview: Segmentation and Classification Workflow.

An overview of the workflow is presented in figure 32. The key focus of this pipeline is to integrate segmentation and classification techniques to generate an automated deep learning pipeline.

8.1 Requirements

The following workflow requirements have been defined to facilitate the creation of a suitable workflow.

Data understanding and preprocessing

The initial stage of any data-driven process necessitates an impartial comprehension of the dataset at hand, accomplished via exploratory analysis to realise its attributes. In this specific project, the images provided are in JPG format. Nonetheless, to initiate a versatile and adaptable pipeline for multiple segmentation or classification tasks at the MPI (Max Planck Institute), it would be more advantageous to process them in TIFF format. This approach offers benefits such as lossless compression, support for multiple channels, and compatibility with various imaging software and libraries typically utilized in scientific and research domains.

In addition to the data format, organizing data within the pipeline is just as critical, including how input data is stored and where outputs are placed. A well-established and standardised filing system enhances data management and workflow efficiency, facilitating access to, distribution of, and collaboration on data. This ensures that the integrity and traceability of the project are maintained.

User-Friendliness

Creating a user-friendly process is a crucial aspect of any project. The primary aim is to develop a straightforward and hassle-free system, reducing the learning curve and ensuring a beneficial and practical user experience. An effective way to achieve this objective is to approach the design from the user's perspective.

The User Pipeline is the part of the workflow that addresses non-technical users in the fields of machine learning or software development. The primary objective is to provide a user-friendly interface that permits users to efficiently use the segmentation and classification features, without requiring them to comprehend the intricacies of the backend processes.

An essential component of the User Pipeline is the accessibility of preconfigured workflows, which streamlines the complexities of data preparation, algorithm selection, and model optimisation. The project offers well-defined workflows that enable users to input their data, select from an array of predetermined options, and receive segmentation and classification results without necessitating advanced technical skills.

A thoughtfully designed user workflow ensures that end-users can effectively leverage the robust segmentation and classification capabilities without confronting technical complexities. This approach enhances the accessibility and usability of the project by creating a more complete and user-friendly environment.

Modularity and Flexibility

Modularity and flexibility are key design principles that underpin the creation of efficient workflows for segmentation and classification. These principles enable the construction of workflows that are versatile and robust, able to handle different types of data, tasks and evolving demands. To attain a high level of modularity, one should consider the following aspects:

1. **Component-Based Structure:** Break the workflow down into modular components or modules, each accountable for a distinct task or operation.
2. **Encapsulation:** Ensure that each module encapsulates its functionality. This means that modules should have defined inputs and outputs, and hide their internal implementation from other modules. Encapsulation enhances code organization and streamlines maintenance.
3. **Reuse:** Design modules/scripts to be reusable across different projects or tasks.
4. **Interchangeability:** Modules should be interchangeable, enabling the substitution of one module with another that performs a corresponding task, without interfering with the entire workflow.
5. **Parameterization:** Allow users and developers to customise the pipeline by offering key parameters as configurable options.

6. **Documentation:** Thoroughly document the structure of the workflow, the purpose and functionality of each component, and guidelines for adding or modifying components. Concise documentation is crucial for comprehending and expanding the pipeline.

Interoperability

Interoperability is a crucial aspect that refers to the workflow's ability to seamlessly integrate and interact with other software tools, data formats and systems commonly used in the discipline. This ensures that workflows can competently communicate with external components and efficiently exchange data. In order to achieve success, it is imperative to manage diverse standard data formats for this project. Additionally, it is essential that the output of this pipeline be used in subsequent processing stages.

Error Handling

These factors guarantee that your workflow can proficiently handle unpredicted occurrences, errors and difficulties that may emerge during data processing, feature extraction, classification or any other phase of the pipeline. At the outset, errors must be identified during various stages of the pipeline, which could include inaccuracies related to data quality, algorithm malfunctions, or unforeseen issues. Additionally, it is essential to implement a comprehensive system for logging errors and exceptions systematically. Ensure that error logs document error types, locations, timestamps, and pertinent contextual information to diagnose and resolve issues effectively. Error logging plays a critical role in problem-solving within user functionalities, and it is crucial to make the logging or error information user-friendly. At this point, it might be advantageous to document common errors, their probable causes, and suggested solutions for correcting them in the workflow's documentation.

Adaptability and Customization

Adaptability and Customization should ensure that the workflow can be modified for new domain-specific requirements. Moreover, this attribute should also enable the pipeline's use for novel and varied initiatives in the future. It is indicative of the models for categorisation and segmentation being easily interchangeable, and subsequent modifications can thus be swiftly executed.

8.2 Implementation

After outlining the criteria for a suitable workflow for image segmentation and classification, this implementation is presented. This implementation provides two essential Python scripts to merge the segmentation with DeLTA 2.0 and the classification with ResNET into one executable pipeline. This implementation should be viewed as a proof of concept and potential foundation for further development.

8.2.1 Data organization

Organisation of data handling is a crucial element of an automated pipeline. To achieve this, workflow scripts were devised for use on Jupyterhub or local machines, and a dedicated folder structure was created. Figure 33 depicts this structure, designed to ensure the scripts can be used with minimum computer proficiency. With the data provided in the

`input_images` directory, the images can be processed by running the scripts without any further modifications.

Figure 33: Directory structure of the automated segmentation and classification pipeline.

The segmentation maps, generated by the pipeline, are saved in the 'binary_masks' folder. Regions of Interest (ROIs) are then extracted and stored in the 'ROIs' folder, before being classified in order to produce resulting data. The final directory, 'classification', contains a CSV file displaying colony tallies by type and accompanying image names.

8.2.2 Application

As previously mentioned, the proposed pipeline scripts can be utilised either in Jupyterhub or locally, with consistent directory structures. Besides, a script for producing classification output from pre-existing binary masks is available.

The Jupyter notebook script designed for execution on a cluster is titled "pipeline.ipynb" and comprises both segmentation and classification steps that can be run altogether. The script's specifications are stored in a JSON file, which can be customised to meet various requirements. In addition, a requirements file with all the essential libraries for execution is also provided. The image files, comprising binary masks, ROIs and the classification CSV file, are saved in the subdirectory introduced in the preceding section.

	Image	mix	smooth	wrinkly	total
1	MIX-01.tif	4	13	6	23
2	MIX-02.tif	20	12	4	36
3	MIX-03.tif	32	9	4	45

Figure 34: Classification results.

A tabulated record of colonies counted in total and by type is contained in a CSV file, with an illustrated example provided in figure 34.

This format facilitates the examination of colony counts within large data sets, potentially enabling novel discoveries in subsequent endeavours.

9 Conclusion

This project aimed to establish an efficient deep learning workflow tailored for the segmentation and classification of SBW 25 colonies. To achieve this, a dataset comprising labeled images was meticulously crafted, requiring substantial manual effort. Manual effort was required due to the insufficient results produced by pre-trained colony segmentation models. A suitable tool, QuPath, was discovered that caters to diverse requirements. The QuPath project created allows for the export of manually created annotations in multiple formats, providing avenues for future investigations. Additionally, a dataset specific to colony classification was gathered.

The first chapters of this thesis presented crucial technologies and metrics required to develop an automated pipeline for image segmentation and classification in thorough detail. The pipeline that was produced highlights proficient methods for seamless execution of these tasks.

A significant achievement of this project was the successfully retrained DeLTA 2.0 for segmentation purposes. The initially developed cell segmentation tool displayed adaptability by effectively segmenting bacteria colonies, a task that differs from its original training data. DeLTA 2.0, after being retrained, achieved remarkable metrics on our test dataset, recording an Accuracy of 0.95 and an IoU of 0.88, thus emphasizing its effectiveness for this new segmentation task.

In contrast, trials with other tools revealed limitations. Notably, the state-of-the-art cell segmentation tool Omnipose exhibited an inherent incapacity for segmentation. Upon investigating the segmentation abilities of large general segmentation models, specifically Segment Anything, promising results were showcased following fine-tuning. Whilst there was variability in segmentation outcomes across different image patches, commendable results were demonstrated by optimal patches, suggesting potential directions for further refinement.

To address these challenges, a range of image operations were implemented but did not lead to any observable improvements in the established metrics. Despite efforts involving specialised thresholds, including adaptive thresholds for image processing, discernible enhancements in results did not materialise.

For the classification task, the ResNet-50 trained model proved to be an appropriate choice as it demonstrated efficiency in distinguishing between the three types of colony. Achieving an Accuracy of 0.95, this model proved to be highly effective.

The developed pipeline for segmentation and classification ensured a seamless integration of image segmentation with colony classification. Furthermore, the included scripts provided ease of use for both local machines and GPU clusters. The pipeline boasts a user-friendly directory structure, enabling simple script execution with minimal user involvement.

Ongoing refinement is necessary for effective application in the specific context of the MPI in Plön, particularly in view of the limited availability of images for model training and refinement.

10 Outlook

This project serves as a crucial step towards future endeavors. The successful retraining of segmentation models for our particular dataset constitutes a noteworthy accomplishment. Nevertheless, additional opportunities for exploration remain in the field.

One of the primary areas in need of enhancement refers to expanding the dataset underpinning the pipeline. Notably limited, the current dataset consists of only 90 images and requires augmentation. Potential improvement: Future endeavours may include the utilization of artificial image creation techniques [69], to produce supplementary colony images. Apart from mere volume, the dataset's quality can be elevated by ensuring uniform image quality.

To enhance the workflow further, there may be a need to explore image segmentation tools more comprehensively. Further investigation of Omnipose, an advanced technology used for segmenting cells, may reveal opportunities for its integration into our specialized model. Additionally, we can develop an enhanced fine-tuning method for Segment Anything, to train more segments and improve performance.

It is important to note that this workflow should be considered as a base concept for a functional pipeline used for segmenting and classifying. With the main focus of this thesis being segmentation selection, future research could concentrate on improving the classification of bacteria colonies.

The classification process highlighted the requirement for more image data to better differentiate among colony varieties. Manual collection or machine learning-generated imagery could both serve as feasible options for expanding the dataset. Subsequently, a potential upcoming project could investigate the classification of the dataset created, with the goal of developing an assessment procedure for colony datasets that utilizes the classification results produced during this project.

The eventual aim is to implement an image processing pipeline that is user-friendly and seamlessly integrates the model into a graphical user interface (GUI). Testing and evaluating available tools which can load deep learning models is vital for reaching this objective and catering to researchers with limited deep learning and scripting knowledge.

Glossary

Area Under the Curve (AUC) The Area Under the Curve (AUC) is a performance measurement for the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve. It provides a measure of the classifier's performance across all possible classification thresholds [21]. 8

Artificial Intelligence Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are capable of learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. For a comprehensive introduction, see [71]. 13

Central Processing Unit (CPU) The Central Processing Unit (CPU) is the primary component of a computer responsible for executing instructions and performing calculations. For a comprehensive discussion, see [72]. 40

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a type of deep neural network designed for tasks involving grid-like data, such as images and videos. For a detailed introduction, see [73]. 1, 2, 10

Deep Learning Deep Learning is a subfield of machine learning that focuses on training artificial neural networks with multiple layers. For a comprehensive reference, see [74]. 1, 2, 13

Features Features refer to the attributes or characteristics of data used as inputs for machine learning models. For the latest insights, refer to [31]. 3, 10

Graphical User Interface (GUI) A Graphical User Interface (GUI) is a visual interface that allows users to interact with a computer program using graphical elements such as windows, icons, buttons, and menus. For a comprehensive discussion, see [75]. 40

Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) A Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) is a specialized electronic circuit designed to accelerate the rendering of images and videos in a computer's memory. For more details, refer to [72]. 40

Neural Network A Neural Network (NN) is a computational model inspired by the structure and function of biological neural networks. It consists of interconnected artificial neurons that process and transmit information. For a comprehensive introduction, see [74]. 5, 10, 13, 14

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve is a graphical plot that illustrates the diagnostic ability of a binary classifier system as its discrimination threshold is varied. It is created by plotting the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) at various threshold settings [21]. 8

A File Appendix

The file appendix contains the training datasets used in this thesis, the test splits and the predicted datasets.

The zip archive is structured as follows:

Morphological Colony Classification

\pipeline

\assets:

Directory contains model files for segmentation and classification network

\input_masks:

Directory to store the images for classification

\binary_masks:

Directory to store the binary masks created by the pipeline

\ROIs:

Directory to store the ROIs extracted from the images with the help of binary masks

\classification:

Directory to store classification output

\QuPath-Project

\instance.groovy:

Script to export instance masks from QuPath

\binary.groovy:

Script to export binary masks from QuPath

\whole directory:

Contains the whole segmentation project in QuPath with the manually created Ground Truth

\development

\omnipose:

Directory contains all scripts and assets from Omnipose experiments

\delta:

Directory contains all scripts and assets from DeLTA 2.0 experiments

\segment-anything:

Directory contains all scripts from Segment experiments

\classification:

Directory contains all scripts and assets for training classifier

\other_scripts:

Directory contains all scripts and assets from the complete Project that are not related to a special framework

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